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Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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Editorial Column

“Let's contour Romania's touristic brand”

In conformity with the statistics of the Tourism World Organization, in the present tourism represents „one of the first world industry (with an affair figure of 3500 milliard USA dollars, the 1st place in the world as for the working force employed (over 6,5% from the occupied population of the globe) and it detains the 2nd-3rd place in the hierarchy of worldwide exports (after the oil industry and construction machine industry)”.

All these positions of the tourism industry in the world society economy is going to get head, so that several specialists appreciate that in the 21st century tourism will represent the biggest economic affair.

In this remarkable trend it must be appreciated the fact that Romania has a big chance through its touristic vocation. It is known that we dispose of important **touristic resources** concretized in the existence of a varied geographic space, biodiversity and a rich cultural diversity, based on valuable historic and art creations and with a particular balneo-climatic potential.

Even though it is the economic branch with the highest international competitive advantage, its economic performances are modest in the present. In our opinion, one of the reasons is still the lack of finding our specificity and identity evident on the tough competitive market of the international tourism industry.

In this context, the typology, individuality and originality of the Romanian tourism must be more emphasized, being necessary the construction of an unmistakable image at the world level.

Elements of world uniqueness or primacy of the Romanians, from different fields of activity, certainly represent the starting bases for the conception of the touristic brand of the country. Without pretensions to find the most representative aspects, we still try a brief enumeration of the ones, unfortunately, forgotten or not sustained at their true value.

Thus, we wonder why Romania isn't sought by tourists as "**Virgin Mary's Garden**" (or "**Romania - Carpathian Garden**"), underlying the exquisite rural space and the remarkable biodiversity of flora and fauna from the Carpathians (big carnivorous, black goats, birds or rare plants, etc.) or the uniqueness of the Danube Delta. At the same time it must be emphasized the unique taste of the agricultural products, much over what exists in countries with intensive-industrial technologies, products that are the basis of tasteful and, at the same time, non sophisticated traditional culinary preparations. We must remind also the Romanian honey, quoted as the most valuable at the world wide level, or the *Fetească neagră* (black Feteasca) wine, specific to Romania.

At music level, we wonder why Romania is not sought as the **"Panpipe country"**, i.e. to claim our worldwide primacy for this instrument, to present musical events all over the world, from folkloric music up to symphony one. Or as **"The country of Doina"** - lyric, solemn, improvised and spontaneous song - unique genre in the world, specific to the Romanian people, expressing varied feelings such as: longing, sadness, love, regret, melancholy. The touristic promotion must show the world that the Doina, the Călușul (little horse) or Horezu Ceramics stand at the same level as the Tango shared by Argentina and Uruguay, the Brazilian Samba, the Canto a tenore from Italy etc.

At sports level, we wonder why Romania isn't sought as **"Oina Country** - forefather of the American baseball", i.e. to claim our worldwide primacy at this type of sport game, to spread it and sustain competitions all over the country, to modernize the playground, to make it more attractive (we have the American success model, with immense financial incomes).

And last, but not least, why Romania isn't sought as **"A country of ancestral and authentic spirit"**, somehow unique all over the world as an approach manner: - complete opening towards divinity and absolute through the churches from Northern Moldavia, having painted exterior for hundreds of years, i.e. in direct connection with Universe; - the mockery of death, with the Happy Cemetery from Săpânța; - the universal essence of the form, given by Brancusi's creations from Tg.Jiu, to give only a few examples among so many others.

An impact have also the folkloric customs and traditions, but also memorable legends from inland or universal literature, as it is known Dracula's legend, in fact one of the few brand consecrated elements for Romania.

Inventorying may, of course, go on... But what is interesting is that, through professionalism, to define and follow a pragmatic strategy in order to impose an original image of the Romanian tourism, i.e. to contour a brand of a unique country at international level.

Prof.univ.dr.ing. **Romulus GRUIA**
Director of publication

INFLUENCE OF CASING THICKNESS (PEAT) ON THE DIMENSIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHAMPIGNON MUSHROOM (AGARICUS BISPORUS A117)

H. GHE. SCHIAU*

Abstract: Analyzing the results appeared accidentally of mushrooms growth cycle, we concluded that a thin layer of casing material cause significant growth of mushrooms size. To demonstrate the influence of casing thickness on the scale I realize a growing test in the mushroom company Kadna Bionatura S.R.L. On 75% of the culture surface we applied a casing of 6.5 to 7 cm (traditional) and the remaining 25% a casing of 4.5 to 5 cm. Test results confirmed that the use of a thin layer of peat, leads to a significant increase of the mushroom dimensions detrimental numerical density, mushrooms *Agaricus Bisporus*, with a minor decrease productivity.

Keywords: casing soil, peat, *Agaricus Bisporus*.

During a period of over a year of cultivation of mushrooms *Agaricus Bisporus* I noticed that in some areas of culture, accidentally appear much larger mushroom than average but numerical lower density. After studies and measurements made in the mentioned areas we found that the casing thickness (peat) was significantly lower. The causes of these errors are caused by improper handling and mixing of the raw materials used.

Because many Romanian customers prefer large mushrooms for their preparation in the oven, we tried to determine the exact conditions required to obtain these large mushrooms

In the farm of Feldioara belonging to SC Kadna Bionatura S.R.L., which has as main activity the cultivation of mushrooms *Agaricus Bisporus* (Champignon) we performed a test cultivation of mushrooms in these circumstances:

I covered compost layer on the shelves no.1,2 and 3 with a layer thickness from 6.5 to 7 cm casing material (traditional) and shelves no 4 with a thin layer of only 4.5 to 5 cm. The result confirmed our initial assumption that mushrooms will grow larger but with a lower density.

To demonstrate the influence of coating thickness on the size mushrooms were used raw materials bought from CNC Netherlands, consisting of 17 tons and 5 tons phase III compost peat (mixed level).

The casing soil is a protective layer with a specific microclimate which helps in the development of fruit bodies. This layer differs from compost in its nutritious properties; it can hold a great amount of water and give it up when necessary. Moreover, a specific environment

is created in the casing layer, and it is favorable for the development of mushroom mycelium and also the microorganisms necessary for mushroom fruiting.

Good casing soil must have the following properties:

- a high moisture capacity and a water-retaining ability;
- an optimal pH level for mycelium growth;
- a firm structure, that doesn't change during the treatment and watering processes, and a sufficient air and water permeability;
- the absence of pests and pathogenic organisms.

Peat is a soil slightly loose, rich in humus, with high water retention. Peat is important for farmers and gardeners, who mix it into soil to improve its structure and to increase acidity. The most important property of peat is retaining moisture in soil when it is dry and yet preventing the excess of water from killing roots when it is wet. Peat can store nutrients although it is not fertile itself. Formed in marshy places by slow and incomplete decomposition of plant - black peat, derived from anaerobic decomposition of plants and animals in the water at the bottom of lakes in the lowlands, is a mineral-rich soil with an acid reaction to neutral wedge ; **Vermiculite** is a hydrous, silicate mineral that is classified as a phyllosilicate and that expands greatly when heated. This process of peeling or swelling is done in ovens specially designed for that purpose. Typical chemical formula (Mg, Ca, K, Fe11) 3 (Si, Al, Fe111) 4O10 (OH) 2O4H2O but there are other variations.

Perlite is an inorganic material that contains silicon dioxide, in a proportion of about 77%, perfectly dry, natural, organic, granular, lightweight, excellent insulating, chemically very stable, non-degradable over time, which does not burn and can be used as efficiently and without any risk, both normal ambient temperatures and in extreme conditions, extreme temperatures of minus 200 degrees C and plus 800 degrees C.

Perlite is obtained by heat treatment of natural pearlitic rock that expands in special ovens at temperatures of about 1000 degrees C.

Feed with compost: After feeding the growing room with compost, we done periodic measurements of temperature because compost Phase III is more active than Phase II compost. In 9 hours the compost temperature increase with 5-6 ° C.

After feeding the shelvets, we immediately leveled horizontally the compost. (Fig. 1-2)

Fig.1

Fig. 2

Casing: After 24 hours of the leveling was done, we start to cover the compost with peat. Thickness of peat, which is of high quality and meets the full requirements of mushrooms, is recommended by the manufacturer of compost, of 6-7 cm. For higher production, we need a

greater amount of water and peat thickness is recommended if it absorbs and retains very easy. Compost temperature was adjusted to 25-26 ° C (measured at 8 points) with cooling / heating with air processing unit.

I decided to cover (for this test) 25% of the grooving surface with a thin layer of only 4 to 4.5 cm. (Fig. 3-4)

Fig.3.

Fig. 4

Table 1

Total growing surface	256 sqm
Traditionally growing surface (6-7 cm)	192 sqm
Test growing surface (4-4,5 cm)	64 sqm

Mycelia development: On cover was made the first watering. The amount of water used was of 2.5-3 l/m.

Watering: Judging from the cover of 2-3 days, we started watering and pesticide treatments with Dinilin and Mirage. In the 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th days, coating mixture was stocked with water, taking into account the temperature, the penetration of mycelium in peat and peat saturation with water.

Daily replenishment water were 2-3-4 l / m.
 Compost temperature 25-27 ° C,
 Humidity 95-98%,
 CO₂ concentration - 4000-5000 ppm.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Scarification (mixing): This work was performed on 8th day after casing, when the mycelium studded at least 2/3 in peat. For a good dispersion was mixed primary intensity to compost surface. Well mixed and loose peat was carefully equalized again to remain granulated and not compacted. Is important because it creates a favorable microclimate for primordial formation. Relative humidity was maintained at a high level - 95-98%.

The concentration of carbon dioxide - more than 6000 ppm,

Fresh air ventilation was stopped 3 days.

Compost temperature 27 to 28 ° C.

Passing on production: The optimum moment is reached when mycelia threads peat surface at a rate of 100%, then we can start fresh air cooling (Fig. 7).

The test area there was a large mushroom watering stress by 0.5 -1 l / m (Fig. 8).

Compost temperature was decreased daily by 1.5 - 2 ° C, the temperature at 17-18 ° C in air and compost temperature was decreased from 25-27 ° C, 19-20 ° C, within 4 days.

- CO₂ concentration from 1500 to 1700 ppm,
- Humidity maintained at 92% to form pea (mushroom size 1-1.5 cm).
- The test layer sprayed water 100 ml / m² twice daily. He kept humidity of 92%. These irrigations were directly supervised by me and technologist.

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

First flush and harvesting: resume watering began after the appearance of mushrooms with a size of 1-1.5 cm in diameter. Proceeded to apply a water quantity of 1.5 l water / sqm indirect splash (rain phenomenon). The amount of water taken is crucial and influences the quantity of production. After watering, ensure continuous ventilation required mushrooms drying in 1-2 hours. If the mushrooms remained water can stain fungi and can lead to diseases and pests

(bacterioza, *Dactylium dendroides*, *Mycogone pernicioso*) and their spread.

18th days from coverage stopped harvesting water for preparation.

Harvesting: We started from the 20th day after feeding.

Compost temperature was 20-21 ° C,

Air temperature 17-18 ° C,

Carbon dioxide from 1500 to 2000 ppm

Humidity of 80-86% throughout production.

At the end you wave were recorded the following amounts:

Table. 2.

Total growing surface	Flush 1	1256 sqm	3740 kg	14,609 kg / m
Traditionally growing surface	Flush 1	1192 sq	2850 kg	14,844 kg / m
Test growing surface	Flush 1	64 sqm	890 kg	13,906 kg / m

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Flush 2 and harvesting 2: resume watering mushrooms after the appearance started with a size of 1-1.5 cm in diameter. Was done as in flush 1 to apply a water quantity of 1.5 l water / sqm indirect splash (rain phenomenon). After

watering, ensure continuous ventilation required mushrooms drying in 1-2 hours. Day 26 from coverage stopped harvesting water for preparation.

Harvesting: It started from the 28th day after introduction. Compost temperature was 19-21 ° C, 17-18 ° C air, carbon dioxide and humidity of 80-86% from 1500 to 2000 ppm throughout production. At the end of wave 2, there were the following amounts:

Table. 3.

Total growing surface	Flush 2	1256 sqm	2900 kg	11,328 kg / m
Traditionally growing surface	Flush 2	1192 sq	2190 kg	11,406 kg / m
Test growing surface	Flush 2	64 sqm	2 710 kg	11,094 kg / m

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

Flush 3 and harvesting 3. The preparation and formation of flush 3 to use less water than the first two flushes, but keeping the same parameters of temperature and carbon dioxide concentration.

Table 4.

Total growing surface	Flush 3	1256 sqm	1425 kg	5,566 kg / m
Traditionally growing surface	Flush 3	1192 sq	1100 kg	5,230 kg / m
Test growing surface	Flush 3	64 sqm	325 kg	5,078 kg / m

Although productivity app is 2% lower if the test variant with reduced coating thickness due to higher commercial value (in Romania), the production value is higher.

In conclusion, based on market demand, mushroom dimensional decide which category to occur at a specific time, simply by changing the coating thickness.

Final results for the three flushes of culture were:

Table 5.

Total growing surface	Flush 1+2+3	1256 sqm	8065 kg	31,504 kg / m
Traditionally growing surface	Flush 1+2+3	1192 sq	6140 kg	31,979 kg / m
Test growing surface	Flush 1+2+3	64 sqm	1925 kg	30,078 kg / m

Fig. 13

Fig. 14

Fig. 15

Fig. 16

Estimated production version of the classic	256 mp	8187 kg	RON 5,50	RON 45,026.67
Estimated production version test	256 mp	7700 kg	RON 6,50	RON 50,050.00

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THERAPEUTICALLY AND PHARMACOLOGICAL VIRTUES OF GOD'S MUSHROOM – AGARICUS BLAZEI MURILL. INHIBITORY EFFECTS IN INFECTION, CANCER AND DIABETES

H. GHE. SCHIAU*

Abstract: *Agaricus blazei Murill (subrufescens)* is an edible mushroom, with a relatively sweet taste and aroma of almonds, originally from Brazil, Piedade area, which was traditionally used against a wide range of diseases including cancer, chronic hepatitis and diabetes. Thanks to its beneficial effects on health, it was taken to Japan and submitted to a thorough biomedical research, which confirmed the richness of immunomodulatory substances, such as β -glucans. Since that time, it has been widely cultivated in Japan for medicinal purposes. Based on sequence analysis of DNA and the mapping studies and genetic analysis of hybrid descendent, there is a strong co-specificity casuistic Brazilian mushroom with *Agaricus Subrufescens*. Scientific studies have focused primarily on the effect that ABM has as immunomodulation agent and its therapeutic effect on various infections and cancers.

According to a clinical study on cancer, which was held in South Korea in 2004, *Agaricus blazei Murill* had improved the quality of life of patients undergoing chemotherapy drugs treatment.

Keywords: Medicinal mushrooms, *Agaricus subrufescens /blazei*, therapeutically virtues, cancer, immune system, ABM

1. History and origin

The Treaty Medical Byzantine discovered in 1902 in the Florentine library, Russian Byzantinist Kh Ed. Loparev (Petersburg), *Agaricus subrufescens* was presented by Lucius Apuleius Platonicus (123/125 AD - 180 AD) as a cure for malignant ulcers of the larynx from the 1st century AD and used until 15th century AD, after which period begins to be forgotten. In 1893 *Agaricus subrufescens* was described by American botanist Charles Horton Peck (1833-1917). From the late 19th to early 20th century it was cultivated for consumption in the eastern United States.

In the last century, more precisely in the '60s, several studies have revealed that, in Brazil, in the mountains Piedade, about 100 km from Sao Paulo, a representative group of people, although living in poverty, has a high and average longevity and they are not affected by infectious diseases, diabetes and cancer. Studying this population nutrition, it was concluded that the main food consumed regularly it is a fungus Agaricaceae family, like *Agaricus Bisporus* (Champignon), but distinguished by several key factors.

Surprising absence of disease and longevity of the local population was soon associated with frequent use of "Cogumelo de Deus", a Brazilian

mushroom whose name literally means fungus from God.

Fig. 1-2. Piedade, geographical location

First to discover the effect of mushroom *Agaricus blazei* Murill was Dr. Takatoshi Furumoto. *Agaricus blazei* has become a serious issue for researchers from different fields, is analyzed for its health benefits. In early 1970, researchers began to study the unusually low rate of geriatric diseases among the people of Piedade. A thorough research of Dr. Tetsuo Ikegawa National Cancer Center, Dr. Shobo Shibata, professor in the Department of Pharmacology of the National University of Tokyo, and other researchers have confirmed the pharmacological actions and therapeutic properties of this rare fungus, native the above-mentioned region, Piedade.

The prevailing climatic conditions of the area, the temperatures during the day of $35^{\circ}\text{C} \div 35^{\circ}\text{C}$, and during the night of $20^{\circ}\text{C} \div 25^{\circ}\text{C}$ and an average humidity of 80%, are ideal for *Agaricus blazei* Murill (ABM).

In fact, the very survival of ABM is affected by the presence of these external conditions (purified air, soil containing wild horse droppings, little rain in the evening). These conditions were carefully monitored and were followed by a series of attempts to cultivate these fungi in various locations worldwide.

Iwaide Inosuke, Professor at the National University of Tokyo, Japan, has succeeded for the first time in the world to cultivate *Agaricus blazei* Murill artificial. Thus obtain enough material for the experiments, the effects of the fungus on various diseases being reported at conferences, congresses, general assemblies of scientific academies professors Hitoshi Ito (physician and pharmacologist, both) and Shimura Keishiro (pharmacologist) Mon National University in Japan. Hybrid obtained they were done studies to which we refer, *Agaricus Max*TM, cultivated supervision of these teachers Iwaide Fungology Research Corporation.

After 1994, ABM mushrooms were introduced and cultivated in several countries: China, Japan, Korea, USA, and Taiwan and, recently, in Belgium and the Netherlands. In Romania there is one company that has achieved remarkable results in increased ABM, variant Milena. Milena fungus was registered with the varieties since 2007, the State Institute for Variety Testing and Registration, Romania (Official Catalogue, 2008, p.37, Mushroom - *Agaricus blazei* Murill, variety name - Milena, maintainer - 1094, Year - 2007).

Table 1. Common names for ABM

Mushroom god	Worldwide
Mushroom of God,	
Piedade mushroom	
Royal fungus	
Almond mushroom	
Mushroom sun	
<i>Agaricus blazei</i> Murill ABM from	
<i>Agaricus Milena</i> -ROMANIA	China
Song Ji Rong	
Himematsutake	Japan
<i>Agaricus</i> utake	
Kawarihiratake	Brazil
Cogumelo do Sol Brazil	
Cogumelo medicinel	

Fig. 3-*Agaricus Blazei* Murill

2. Background and composition

Of the approximately 20,000 types of mushrooms classified in the world, only about 300 are edible. The research was mainly focused on varieties that can be used in intensive culture both for industrial and medicinal purposes.

Agaricus blazei Murril is a mushroom belonging to numerous families with pharmacological and therapeutic for human virtues.

Table 2. Systematic classification of ABM

Regn	Fungi
Subregn	Dikarya
Division	Basidiomycota
Subdivision	Agaricomycotina
Class	Agaricomycetes sau Homobasidiomycetes
Subclass	Homobasidiomycetidae
Order	Agaricales
Family	Agaricaceae

Genus	Agaricus
Species	sn. Agaricus blazei Murill,
	sn. Agaricus blazei Heinemann,
	sn. Agaricus subrufescens Peck

Following a lengthy analysis and testing laboratory, it was established that the main component of the 18 amino acids, 10 minerals, 16 different vitamins, 46 enzymes, ergosterol, linoleic acid and polysaccharides highlighted, is 1-3/1-6 beta-glucan. High levels of beta-glucan in its three forms of β -(1-3)-D-glucan, β -(1-4)-D-glucan, and β -(1-6)-D-glucan, has designed to stimulate immune cells such as NK cells, macrophages, dendritic cells and polymorphonuclear leukocytes.

Table 3. The chemical composition of ABM

Chemical composition:	100 g dry	
Energy	288,00	kcl
Protein	38,50	g
Fat	2,60	g
Carbohydrates	27,70	g
β -glucan	12,40	g
Fiber	20,60	g
Sodium	8,40	g
Calcium	8,40	mg
Iron	22,50	mg
Potassium	10,10	mg
Magneziu	925,00	mg
Zinc	96,50	mg
Copper	7,87	mg
Manganese	7,67	mg
Iodine	0,83	mg
Vitamin B1	0,63	mg
Vitamin B2	3,04	mg
Vitamin B6	0,54	mg
Niacin	33,50	mg
Pantotenic Acid	22,90	mg
Folic Acid	230,00	mcg
Biotin	123,00	mcg
Vitamin D	56,70	mcg
Agaritin	15,30	ppm

This mushroom is found in abundance of antioxidant substances and other substances that are designed to stimulate immune cells to increase production of cytokines (Antigen is the term that defines any endogenous or exogenous origin substance, which in the body is not

recognized as its own and cause an immune response, aimed at neutralizing and removing them).

Generally known active compounds in Agaricus blazei Murill include beta-glucans, Ergosterol (provitamin D2) derivatives, Glucomannan, Mannogalactoglucan, Proteoglucans and Riboglucans.

Phytocomplex of polysaccharides is thought to be responsible for its immune stimulating and anti-tumor, probably about the biochemical opsonization (opsonizing, in English, is the process by which antigens are bound to act on molecules marked antibody). Dr. Hirokazu Kawagishi at Shizuoka University was the first who managed to separate compounds with anticancer activity by purifying sodium hydroxide extract of ABM mushrooms. The author was able to determine apparent polysaccharides with antitumor activity. Currently, clinical trials provide multiple confirmations positive, however, studies are still needed to fully assess.

Market, including the Romanian, appeared a lot of ABM extracts. Each manufacturer has their own recipe based on its own laboratories with specific destinations (diabetes, cancer, Immunostimulators) and additional active ingredients (erinaceum Hericium, Grifola frondosa, Ganoderma lucidum, aloe Vera, etc.). How very mushroom harvesting period and layer growth components (i.e. compost) determines the relative variations of concentrations of active agents, it is important to be mentioned these things to therapeutic recommendations.

In the experiment conducted by a research group led by Professors Hitoshi Ito and Shimura Keishiro in Japan, the preparation of Agaricus blazei Murill was administered to mice implanted with cancer. Their complete recovery rate was found to be 90.4% and the rate of progress was halting 99.4%. The results were reported at the general meeting of the Japanese Academy of Mycology, Pharmacology and Cancer.

From studies done on mice, it was determined that the most effective preparation comprises the following extracts: 82% ABM, 15% Hericium erinaceum (Japanese: Yamabushitake) and 3% Grifola frondosa (Maitake), all three belonging to the same family of the Basidiomycetes. This reduced the number of bacteria susceptible mice infected blood and increased animal survival test. Following the success obtained in tests done on mice, have

followed a series of tests on humans suffering from various diseases.

Methods of treatment of various cancers generally used today are: surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy (anticancer agent administration). But in any case, adverse reactions are severe and induce additional suffering patients. Manner as complementary treatment and / or alternative to the usual methods of treatment, immunotherapy now gaining increasingly more ground. Immunotherapy substantially reduce suffering and pain caused by the side effects inherent caused by cancer, cancer terminal and prevent its recurrence by stimulating the body's immune factors. Administration of AMB in different forms, extract, powder, tinctures and teas dried mushrooms had remarkable effects on functional systems:

3. ABM consumption benefits. Study of the effects and composition

Anti-tumor effect:

- Activates the immune system of the host (macrophage) and of the reticule-endothelial system.
- Stimulates induction of cytokine (interferon-site), acts as BRM and prolongs life.
- Has anti-tumor effect by 20-25% higher than *Lentinus* species, *Flammulina velutipes*, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Pholiota nameko*, etc., suppressing cell proliferation.
- Carcinostatic action (action to suppress the spread of HeLa cells), blocking the spread of cancer cells with cytotoxin steroids.

Effect cancer prevention:

-Excretory carcinogenic effect of absorbed dietary fiber, beta-D-glucan digestible heteropolizaharide, chitin, etc..

Reducing sugar:

-Cure for diabetes by polysaccharides (beta-D-glucan), polysaccharide protein complex, RNA complex, stimulating the production of insulin by the pancreas function invigorated by bringing amino acids and zinc.

Lower blood pressure, lower cholesterol, remedy for arteriosclerosis:

- Unsaturated fatty acids and linolenic acid (comprising the dietary fiber) and fat
- Adjusts vascular tone and blood pressure, inhibit vasoconstriction by magnesium protects blood vessels by phenyl-alanine and vitamin C, prevents atherosclerosis by manganese and

selenium, it has diuretic effect in potassium and magnesium.

Action of vitamin D2:

- Cure for osteoporosis due to rich in vitamin D obtained by drying in the sun *Agaricus blazei* mushrooms, contributes to calcium absorption, stimulates bone production by ergosterol.

Strengthening the immune system, thus preventing the occurrence of malignant tumors:

- Modulation of immune system activity, *Agaricus Blazei* is recognized in treating skin allergies, pollinosis, etc. and the endocrine system, regulating the secretion of thyroid and gonadal
 - Adjust the thyroid secretion due to beta (1.6) D glucan and selenium and iodine phenyl-alanine
 - The anti-inflammatory due sterol compounds are useful both in chronic rheumatic diseases and to combat adverse effects of conventional cancer treatments.
 - Protection against hepatitis virus. Beta-D-glucan stimulates the production of interferon own the content of arginine, methionine, copper and vitamin K
 - Stimulates the production of red blood cells by vitamin B12, folic acid, iron, copper, cobalt, tryptophan
 - Favors intestinal absorption by glutamine and threonine and regulate the metabolism of uric acid by molybdenum
- #### Detoxify the body:
- The high content of dietary fiber promotes detoxification by eliminating carcinogens, prevents constipation, stimulates detoxification due to its content of cellulose, pectin and chitin.
 - Pectin and lignin also facilitates the absorption of carbohydrates and lipids.
 - Stimulates nerve transmission and the central nervous system by potassium calming effect by phenyl-alanine, valine, tryptophan and copper histidine and magnesium.
 - Adjusts muscle contraction by calcium, magnesium, lysine and valine
 - Stimulates collagen regeneration through capillary and epithelial, tryptophan, copper, methionine
 - Keep the reproductive function by zinc, arginine

4. The clinical effects of the mushroom *Agaricus blazei* on systems / devices

4.1. Digestive

Duodenal ulcer, hepatocirrhosis, hypertrophy of the liver, liver cancer, stomach cancer, gastritis,

gastric ulcer, gastroptosa, constipation, chronic stomatitis, Pyorrhea alveolaris, polyps, hepatitis B, rectal cancer, sigmoid colon cancer, virus enteritis, etc.

4.2. Circulatory system

High blood pressure, low blood pressure, heart disease, cerebral thrombosis, hemiplegia, severe pneumonia, septicemia, leukemia, malignant lymphogranuloma, Hodgkin's disease, Basedew disease, lung cancer.

4.3. Genital

Mastitis, breast cancer, uterine cancer, ovarian cancer, cervical cancer, disorders caused by menopause.

4.4. Cranial nerve metabolism

Diabetes, multiple articular rheumatism, chronic articular rheumatism, ataxia self, neurosis, Japanese encephalitis.

4.5. Urinary

Cystitis, nephritis, renal failure, prostatomegalie, nephrosis.

4.6. The skin

Dermatophytosis, eczema, dermatitis atypical dermatomiosotis, choriocarcinoma.

4.7. Other

Shoulder pain, muscular dystrophies, hangover, Ozen, arthritis, flu

Clinical effects above list was compiled by the Japanese Cancer Association and the Japanese Pharmaceutical Association.

In the future, tests should be made on the doses to be administered to patients for these diseases. Studies should focus specifically on the effects of cancer and virus, they are one of the biggest debates in the medical world. We believe that the mushroom *Agaricus blazei* Murill also will meet all the tests.

CONCLUSIONS

- This mushroom contains a special class of polysaccharides known as beta-glucan, a potent stimulator of the immune system by activating macrophages, B lymphocytes, natural killer cells and T suppressor cells
- It is a powerful adjuvant in cancer treatment, a very good antioxidant, works very effectively against free radicals, and also helps to lower cholesterol.

- Content-rich rejuvenating elements for human body, make use of these mushrooms a magic cure to treat all diseases, some of them very serious, such as:

- Cancer, diabetes, hepatitis, renal disease, cardiovascular disease,
- Rheumatism, hypertension, hypotension, angina, thrombosis, angiosternoze, hemiplegia,
- Septicemia, leukemia, lymphoma, etc..

- antitumor effect is given by the high content of effective items that:

- Type polysaccharide beta (1.3) D glucan
- Type polysaccharide beta (1.6) D glucan
- Protein compounds
- Ribonucleic acid
- Heteroglucan acid
- Xiloglucan
- Lecithin, etc..

- Reducing effect of these compounds in blood glucose, keeping blood sugar within normal biological.

- When these elements are introduced into white blood cells, facilitates macrophage cell activity (those that destroy or delay the spread of cancer cells).

- Natural esterooids, known for their anticancer effect of the different chemical, used in excess, can cause cancer themselves.

- High content of indigestible fiber has the ability to absorb the carcinogenic substances from the body and eliminate them.

- High content of fibre and unsaturated fatty acid has the effect of reducing blood pressure, cholesterol and arteriosclerosis.

- High amounts of vitamin B1 and B2 and ergosterol

- Under the action of heat (through drying) is converted to vitamin D2, with excellent results in the treatment of osteoporosis

- In conclusion, beta glucan

- Boosts longevity
- Is immuno-stimulating
- Is anticancer.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF SOME SAMPLES OF *AJUGA REPTANS* L. AND *AJUGA GENEVENSIS* L.

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Abstract: Continuing a series of investigations regarding the chemical variability of some vegetal species, we initiated a comparative chemical study of the *Ajuga reptans* L. and *Ajuga genevensis* L. species used in Romanian folk medicin. We investigated the iridoidic, flavonoidic fractions as well as those of the polyphenolcarboxylic acids with the help of such investigation techniques as: thin layer chromatography, spectrophotometry and high performance liquid chromatography. We could notice that *Ajuga reptans* is richer in antimflammatory, immunomodulating and hepatoprotecting iridoids than *Ajuga genevensis*, while the second has a slightly higher content of antioxidant and diuretic polyphenols. By means of HPLC we proved the presence in the studied vegetal material of chlorogenic and caffeic acid, of apigenol and luteolin-7-O-glucosyde.

Keywords: *Ajuga reptans* L., *Ajuga genevensis* L., chemical variability, iridoids, polyphenols.

1. Introduction

Ajuga reptans L. is a plant used in the traditional medicine of many countries from the centre and, especially, the eastern part of Europe.

The extracts obtained from bugle (*Ajuga reptans* L.) are used due to the content of polyphenols of the flavonoidic and polyphenolcarboxylic acids type (due to its antioxidant, vascular and antimicrobial qualities), as well as of iridoids (antiinflammatory and wound healing) as antidiarrhoeaic, antileucoreic, hepatoprotecting and vulnerar. Unlike bugle, blue bugleweed, *Ajuga genevensis* L., is used only in our country as a substitute of the medicinal species, as, due to the fact that it is not very demanding as to the pedoclimatic conditions, it is largely outspread in the wild flora.

In our researches, we have comparatively analysed the chemical composition of four samples *Ajuga reptans* L. And five of *Ajuga genevensis* L. harvested at the beginning of May 2010 in the north eastern part of Moldavia.

The objective of the investigation was to establish the chemical similarities and differences between the two species especially regarding the

composition of the iridoidic, flavonoidic and polyphenolic acid fractions.

The aims of the phytochemical study were to determine the biosynthetic level of the flavonoidic, iridoidic or caffeic/chlorogenic acid type derivates, as well as the influence of some genetic factors (the belonging of the species to the same genus) or environmental (soil and climate), particular and different, also depending on the location of the analysed natural population. Our studies were performed on the vegetal material harvested in 2010.

2. Material and Method

The vegetal material of *Ajuga reptans* L. and *Ajuga genevensis* L. samples harvested at the beginning of May 2010 from natural populations identified in the north of Moldavia was dried at room temperature and extracted with absolute methanol (DER=0.5:100g/mL), at warm temperature, till exhaustion. These extracts served to achieve the spectrophotometric determinations of polyphenols and iridoids.

The TLC and HPLC analyses were performed on extracts for which the ratio drug/extract

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(DER) was of 3:100 g/mL. The analysed samples were prelevated due to the data in table 1.

Table 1. The origin of the vegetal material (2010)

Sample code	Location	Altitude (m)	Collection date
<i>Ajuga reptans</i> L 2010			
AR1	Guranda	171	04.05
AR2	Baisa	282	04.05
AR3	Bicaz-Baraj	560	06.05
AR4	Potoci	648	06.05
<i>Ajuga genevensis</i> L 2010			
AG1	Albesti	70	04.05
AG2	Draslea	100	04.05
AG3	Stancenii	176	04.05
AG4	Baisa	282	04.05
AG5	Grozavesti	530	04.05

To get an idea of the iridoidic and triterpenic spectrum existing in the prelevated plants, we initially achieved a TLC study using the exhaustings with DER 3:100 g/mL [2].

The spectrophotometric determinations aimed the biosynthetic level of the above mentioned secondary metabolites, the analysed methanolic extracts having the DER 0.5:100 g/mL. In these extracts we determined the flavonoids by a treatment with aluminium chloride when the bioactive components form internal complexes with Al^{3+} , intensely yellow coloured, for which the extinction was read on the spectrophotometer at $\lambda=413$ nm, using luteolin as standard [3]. The polyphenolic acid dosing was performed by treating the extracts with phosphowolframic acid in an alkaline medium, when we obtained blue colourings, colourimeted at $\lambda=660$ nm, compared to the chlorogenic standard [3]. **The iridoids** extracted from the vegetal product and purified by passing the extract over a silicagel column, were treated with PABA in acid medium, when, at warmth, there forms a blue coloured compound to be colourimeted at $\lambda=590$ nm, the standard curve being traced with aucuboside [4, 5, 6, 7]. The methanolic exhaustings for which DER was equal to 3:100g/mL were also qualitatively and half-quantitatively analysed by HPLC for polyphenols.

Chromatography conditions:an HPLC Agilent 1100 system with registration and integration of

the chromatograms by means of the Borwin computerized system and multidiode detector.

The stationary phase: eclipse XDB-C18 (150mm x 4,6mm; 5 μ m); **The mobile phase:** component A=sodium acetate 2mM adus la pH=2.5 with acetic acid; cpmponent B=acetonitryl; **gradient:** 98% A;2% B (0-20 min.); 86% A:14%B (20-40 min.); 80%A:20% B (40-50 min.); 70%A:30B (50-60 min.); 98%A:2%b (after 65 min.); **flow:** 1mL/min.; **temperature** in the column compartment 25⁰C; **detection:** UV 320nm for samples and standards; in addition for each standard we registered the absorbtion spectrum in the interval of 200-400nm; **applied volume:** 100 μ L fir the solutions to be analysed and the standard.

3. Results and Discussions

The important part of our study was the comparative phytochemical analysis of the two *Ajuga* species to draw conclusions regarding the inter and intraspecific chemical variability. To monitorize the similarities and differences of chemism in the triterpenic and iridoidic fractions, we analysed the two methanolic *Ajuga* exhausts by the TLC method. In fig.1 and 2 are the thin layer chromatograms for the terpenes and iridoids of the *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* samples.

Figure 1. TLC for terpenes of *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* samples

Legend: samples- v. tab.1; standards: β -sitosterol (B), stigmasterol (S), oleanolic acid (O), ursolic acid (U)

Figure 2. TLC for iridoids of *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* samples.

Legend: samples-v. tab.1; standards: aucuboside (Au), harpagide (Hp), 8-O-acetyl harpagide (8-Hg)

Regarding the iridoids identified in the *Ajuga* extracts, they seem to be represented by two components in both species, out of which the inferior one ($R_f=0.53$) seems to be harpagide, and the second remaining unknown due to the lack of the corresponding standard. A third spot, superior but slight, appears in the case of two *Ajuga reptans* samples (AR3 and AR4) and one *Ajuga genevensis* (AG5) and seems to belong to the 8-O-acetyl harpagide.

If from TLC study produced the main conclusion was the confirmation of the similar chemism in the same species, the highlighting of the differences between the two species respectively, the spectrophotometric dosings of the flavonoids, polyphenolic acids and iridoids produced differentiated quantitative assertions.

In table 2 we present the results obtained by the quantitative determinations.

Table 2. The content in iridoids and polyphenols dosed in vegetal material (*Ajuga reptans* L./*Ajuga genevensis* L.) prelevated from different natural populations in 2010.

Sample Code	Origin	Determination in 100g herba		
		Iridoids	Flavonoids	Polyphenolic acids
		g aucubosid %	g luteolin %	g chlorogenic acid %
<i>Ajuga reptans</i> L.				
AR1	Guranda	1.329 ± 0.0097	0.501 ± 0.0034	1.581 ± 0.0022
AR2	Baisa	1.078 ± 0.0032	0.471 ± 0.0047	1.690 ± 0.0016
AR3	Bicaz – Baraj	1.983 ± 0.0010	0.455 ± 0.0066	1.870 ± 0.0013
AR4	Potoci	1.673 ± 0.0085	0.563 ± 0.0019	1.744 ± 0.0031
<i>Ajuga genevensis</i> L.				
AG1	Albesti	0.988 ± 0.0059	0.698 ± 0.0012	2.020 ± 0.0074
AG2	Draslea	0.8763 ± 0.0036	0.839 ± 0.0011	1.876 ± 0.0061
AG3	Stauceni	0.641 ± 0.0071	0.561 ± 0.0093	1.825 ± 0.0002
AG4	Baisa	1.033 ± 0.0081	0.417 ± 0.0055	1.593 ± 0.0035
AG5	Grozavesti	0.9512 ± 0.0099	0.545 ± 0.0043	1.733 ± 0.0006

As may be noticed, the *Ajuga reptans* samples are richer in immunomodulating and anti-inflammatory iridoids, while in case of *Ajuga genevensis* the antioxidant polyphenol content is higher than in the case of bugle.

If we graphically represent the values from the table, we will notice that regarding the iridoids (fig. 3) the richest sample proved to be *Ajuga reptans* harvested at Bicaz-Baraj, the other bugle samples having a lower content.

Figure 3. The graphic expression of the iridoid content determined in the *Ajuga* exhausts (2010)

Compared to this intraspecific variability determined for the iridoidic fraction of bugle, *Ajuga genevensis* presents a similar situation, yet this time the highest non-volatile monoterpene content being found in the Baisa sample, and the most reduced in that of Stauceni.

On the other hand, it is obvious that along with the intraspecific variability, there also is a genetic, interspecific, variability, *Ajuga reptans* being much richer in iridoids than blue bugleweed.

Figure 4. The graphic expression of the flavonoid content determined in the *Ajuga* exhausts (2010)

Regarding the flavonoids, (fig. 4), we notice that the richest sample in such compounds is that of *Ajuga genevensis* from Draslea, *Ajuga reptans* containing smaller flavonoid quantities. Comparing the values of the Baisa *Ajuga reptans* with those of

Ajuga genevensis of the same location, we notice that the quantitative differences in case of the three fractions of active principles are not major (fig. 5), for the same location, the climatic and soil conditions being identical for the two species.

Figure 5. The graphic expression of the iridoid and polyphenol content determined in methanolic extracts (DER 0,5:100) of bugle and blue bugleweed harvested in the same location-Baisa-in 2010

To better appreciate the similarities and differences of the polyphenolic spectrum of the nine *Ajuga* samples, we resorted to the HPLC analysis. In table 3 we present the

components as well as the corresponding exhausts (DER 3:100 g/mL). quantities identified the polyphenols in

Table 3. Polyphenols identified in *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* methanolic exytracts (2010)

Sample code	Chlorogenic acid		Caffeic acid		Luteolin 7-O-glucoside		Apigenol	
	ug/mL	mg/100g	ug/mL	mg/100g	ug/mL	mg/100g	ug/mL	mg/100g
<i>Ajuga reptans</i> L								
AR1	3.62	12.08	0.97	3.25	0.35	1.17	1.43	4.76
AR2	1.52	5.07	0.97	3.25	0.14	0.48	0.63	2.11
AR3	2.97	9.90	1.23	4.10	0.09	0.31	3.07	10.25
AR4	2.03	6.77	1.32	4.39	0.15	0.84	1.30	4.33
<i>Ajuga genevensis</i> L								
AG1	4.21	14.05	1.06	3.55	0.51	1.72	1.49	4.98
AG2	9.73	32.44	1.60	5.34	0.94	3.15	3.90	12.99
AG3	6.01	20.05	1.73	5.77	1.00	3.32	2.83	9.43
AG4	44.68	148.93	0.83	2.77	1.55	5.16	3.15	10.50
AG5	7.08	23.61	2.07	6.90	1.53	5.10	3.94	13.15

Calculating the concentrations of the chlorogenic acids, caffeic acids, luteolin-7-O-glucoside and apigenol existing in the 100 g of vegetal product, we obtained the values

indicated by the same table 3. Expressing these concentrations graphically, we have the situation from fig. 6.

Figure 6. The variation of the content in chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, luteolin-7-O-glucoside and apigenol (g/100g *herba*) determined by HPLC in the samples of *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* (2010)

One can notice that of the two quantitatively better represented, there poliphenolic acids, the chlorogenic one is appearing, as already seen, great intraspecific

variations, yet especially interspecific. The second polyphenolic acid, the caffeic acid has a smaller concentration, still the *Ajuga genevensis* are richer in this component.

Coming back to the achieved spectrophotometric determinations, we will notice that the majority of the components of the group were not identified. Thus, we have the question of how many more, not identified acids, are there in the vegetal products.

Analogous, we notice that out of the flavonoidic fraction, we could identify only two components: apigenol and luteolin-7-O-glucoside. In this case, apigenol dominates, yet we again notice that the *Ajuga genevensis* populations seem to be richer in this flavonic aglicon than those of *Ajuga reptans*. Again, there arises the question of what flavonoids coexist in *Ajuga genevensis* L. and *Ajuga reptans* L.

Conclusions

The comparative phytochemical study on the two *Ajuga* species, *Ajuga reptans* and *Ajuga genevensis* aimed to highlight the qualitative and quantitative variations of the iridoidic, flavonoidic and polyphenolic acids fractions in dry vegetal material. We noticed that, in both species, the individuals originated from populations developed in different locations, present variations of larger or more restricted limits especially quantitative and less qualitative for the same group of secondary metabolites.

Ajuga reptans proved to be richer in iridoidic components of the harpagide type (antiinflammatory, hepatoprotecting and immunomodulating) while *Ajuga genevensis* is slightly richer in polyphenols (antioxidant and diuretic). Out of the polyphenolic components, by HPLC, we identified and quantified chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, apigenol and luteolin-7-O-glucoside.

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ETHNOBOTANICAL STUDY OF MEDICINAL FLORA USED BY THE PEOPLE OF THE FOREST OF EL HAOURANE - M'SILA - (ALGERIA)

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Abstract: *The region of El Haourane presents an important floristic and ecological diversity including exceptional medicinal flora, this work is just to develop this medicinal flora. Ethnobotanical surveys were conducted in the study area (16 women and 41 men of various ages) using 250 question cards. Therapeutic uses charged by the local population, allowed us to inventory a number of 65 medicinal species in that region and the different types of diseases that affect humans particularly in terms of systems : digestive, respiratory, circulatory, etc.*

Keywords: *El Haourane, medicinal flora, ethnobotanical survey.*

1. Introduction

Les plantes médicinales demeurent encore une source de soins médicaux dans les pays en voie de développement. En outre, la médecine traditionnelle a toujours occupé une place importante dans les traditions de médication en Algérie, grâce à l'utilisation des plantes médicinales qui font partie des moyens de subsistance de la population riveraine. Notre travail constitue une contribution au recensement des plantes utilisées dans la région d'El Haourane, qui présente une diversité floristique et écologique assez importante notamment une flore médicinale exceptionnelle. La valorisation de cette flore, à notre connaissance empêche la forte pression de cueillette qui conduit à la réduction et/ou à la perte de la biodiversité et la diminution de la productivité de la biomasse végétale.

2. Localisation de la zone d'étude

La forêt d'El Haourane est localisée à environ 15km au Nord de la commune de Hammam Dalaâ (wilaya de M'sila), entre les coordonnées suivantes: (Latitude 35°36'-35°59' Nord, X (651,80-657,85) et Longitude 4°23'-4°27' Est, Y

(295,15-299.55). Cette zone d'étude s'étend sur une superficie de 994,56 ha, limitée au Nord par Gribissa, à l'Est par Douar Dréat, à l'Ouest par Sidi Amar et Machrarine, et au Sud par Boustéila (Figure no. 1).

3. Méthode d'étude

Les enquêtes ethnobotaniques ont été réalisées durant la période de mars - avril 2006 au niveau des régions suivantes : El Haourane, Hammam Dalaâ (le souk y compris), Douar Dréat, Sidi Amar et El Baât. Des fiches questionnaires [1] ont été préalablement établies (250 Fiches questionnaires), 57 personnes de différents âges sont interrogés (12 < âge < 83 ; 16 femmes et 41 hommes). Les informations sont obtenus d'une façon générale en posant des questions directes aux informateurs (guérisseurs ou tradipraticiens, herboristes et villageois) de la zone d'investigation. Les informations fournies, ont été notées régulièrement sur des fiches d'enquêtes, ces dernières regroupent deux ensembles d'informations concernant, l'informateur et la végétation. L'identification des échantillons, récoltés sur le terrain, a été faite au laboratoire de botanique du département des sciences de la nature et de la vie, université de M'sila, à l'aide des herbiers disponibles et d'un certain nombre d'ouvrages essentiels [2,3].

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Figure no 1: Localisation de la zone d'étude

4. Résultats et discussion

Les résultats présentés dans cette étude ont été discutés à l'aide des tableaux (Tab.1-7) réalisés à partir des traitements des données qui touchent les guérisseurs, les herboristes et les informateurs ainsi que les plantes utilisées dans cette zone d'étude. Bref, parmi les personnes enquêtées, 26 ont choisies le traitement médical, 21 personnes les soins traditionnels et en fin 10 personnes ont

opté pour les deux. Les enquêtes ethnobotaniques ont révélées que la majorité des espèces médicinales sont utilisées principalement contre les maladies comme : la toux, le rhume, les petites blessures et la diarrhée etc. La décoction constitue le mode de préparation le plus fréquent, suivie par la préparation en poudre et ensuite les autres modes à savoir le cataplasme, macération, nature, fumigation, goutte, infusion et autres.

Tableau no1 : La distribution des informateurs selon les régions et le sexe

Régions	Hommes	Femmes
El Haourane	18	9
Hammam Dalaâ (+ le souk)	17 + 1	3 + 0
Douar Dréat	3	1
Sidi Amar	2	0
El Baât	0	3
Total	41	16
	57	

Tableau no. 2 : La distribution des classes d'âges des informateurs selon les régions

Régions	Classes d'âges (ans)					
	12-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50-60	> 60
El-Haourane	3	7	3	0	2	12
Hammam Dalaâ (+ le souk)	0 + 0	3 + 1	5 + 0	2 + 1	3 + 0	6 + 0
Douar Dréat	0	2	0	0	2	1
Sidi Amar	0	0	1	0	0	0
El Baât	3	0	0	0	0	0
Total	6	13	9	3	7	19

Tableau no 3 : La nature du traitement au niveau de chaque région

Régions	Les types des traitements (soins)		
	médicaux	traditionnels	Les deux
El Haourane	12	10	3
Hammam Dalaâ (+ le souk)	6 + 0	11 + 0	5 + 1
Douar Dréat	3	0	1
Sidi Amar	2	0	0
El Baât	3	0	0
Total	26	21	10

Tableau no 4 : La liste des plantes médicinales de la forêt d'El Haourane

Nom scientifique		
1- <i>Ajuga iva</i> (L.) Scherb.	23- <i>Erica arborea</i> L.	45- <i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> L
2- <i>Allium arscalicum</i> L.	24- <i>Ferula communis</i> L .	46- <i>Plantago albicans</i> L
3- <i>Allium cepa</i> L.	25- <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L	47- <i>Punica granatum</i> L.
4- <i>Allium sativum</i> L.	26- <i>Globularia alypum</i> L.	48- <i>Quercus coccifera</i> L.
5- <i>Ampelaudesma mauritanicum</i> (Poiret) Dur. et Sch.	27- <i>Inula viscosa</i> (L.) Ait.	49- <i>Quercus ilex</i> L.
6- <i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L.	28- <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L.	50- <i>Retama retam</i> Webb.
7- <i>Artemisia campestris</i> L.	29- <i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> L	51- <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.
8- <i>Artemisia herba alba</i> Asso.	30- <i>Lauris nobilis</i> L.	52- <i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L.
9- <i>Asphodelus microcarpus</i> Salzm. Et Viv.	31- <i>Laserpitium gummiferum</i> Desf.	53- <i>Ruta chalepensis</i> L.
10- <i>Asparagus acutifolius</i> L.	32- <i>Lavandula dentata</i> L.	54- <i>Salvia verbenaca</i> (L.) Briq.
11- <i>Beta vulgaris</i> L	33- <i>Lycium europaeum</i> L.	55- <i>Salvia officinalis</i> L.
12- <i>Borago officinalis</i> L.	34- <i>Malva sylvestris</i> L.	56- <i>Saponaria vaccaria</i> L..
13- <i>Calycotome spinosa</i> (L) Lamk.	35- <i>Mentha longifolia</i> (L.) Huds.	57- <i>Scorzonera undulta</i> Vahl
14- <i>Chamaerops humilis</i> L.	36- <i>Marrubium vulgare</i> L.	58- <i>Stipa tenacissima</i> L.
15- <i>Cichorium intybus</i> L	37- <i>Nerium oleandre</i> L.	59- <i>Teucrium polium</i> L.
16- <i>Colocynthis vulgaris</i> (L.) Schrad.	38- <i>Olea europaea</i> Var.	60- <i>Thapsia garganica</i> L.
17- <i>Cynodon dactylon</i> L.	39- <i>Olea oleastre</i> (L.) Dc.	61- <i>Thymelaea hirsuta</i> Endl.
18- <i>Cynara cardunculus</i> L.	40- <i>Origanum glandulosum</i> Desf.	62- <i>Thymus ciliates</i> Desf.
19- <i>Centaureum umbellatum</i> (Gibb) Beck.	41- <i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L.	63- <i>Triticum villosum</i> (L.) M.B.
20- <i>Cynoglossum montanum</i> Lamk.	42- <i>Peganum harmala</i> L.	64- <i>Urtica pilulifera</i> L.
21- <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill	43- <i>Pimpinella lutea</i> Desf.	65- <i>Ziziphus lotus</i> (L.) Desf.
22- <i>Ecbalium elaterium</i> A. Rich.	44- <i>Pinus halepensis</i> L.	

Tableau no. 5 : La distribution des usages selon les fiches questionnaires et les espèces végétales

Usages	Nombre de fiches	Nombre d'espèces
Médicinal	190	51
Alimentaire	37	20
Fourrager	16	13
Aromatique	10	7
Toxique	6	3
Autres	28	16
Total	250	65

Tableau no. 6 : La liste des indications thérapeutiques des plantes inventoriées

Indications thérapeutiques	Nombre de citations	Nom scientifique
Antiulcéreux	02	<i>Olea europaea, Quercus ilex.</i>
Antiprurigineux	01	<i>Asparagus acutifolius</i>
Anti-verrues	02	<i>Asparagus acutifolius, Allium sativum.</i>
Anti-dorsalgie	04	<i>Peganum harmala, Thapsia garganica.</i>
Anticatarrhale	09	<i>Papaver rhoeas, Thymus ciliatus, Olea europaea, Inula viscosa, Allium cepa, Ecbalium elaterium, Origanum glandulosum, Artemisia herba alba, Marrubium vulgare, Ziziphus lotus.</i>
Antidiarrhéique	03	<i>Thapsia garganica, Juniperus phoenicea, Artemisia herba.</i>
Antirhumatismal	06	<i>Inula viscosa, Thapsia garganica, Malva sylvestris, Peganum harmala, Thymelaea hirsuta.</i>
Antipyrétique	01	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>
Antiparasitaire	01	<i>Stipa tenacissima</i>
Antiasthmatique		<i>Pistacia lentiscus, Peganum harmala.</i>
Anti-leishmania	02	<i>Allium arscalonicum, Urtica pilulifera.</i>
Anti-acnéique	02	<i>Mentha longifolia, Lavandula dentata.</i>
Antifongique	03	<i>Olea europaea, Thymelaea hirsuta, Urtica pilulifera.</i>
Antihémorragique	02	<i>Plantago albicans, Rosmarinus officinalis.</i>
Anti-colique	02	<i>Quercus ilex, Rosmarinus officinalis.</i>
Antiémétique	02	<i>Allium sativum, Artemisia herba.</i>
Anti-obsique	01	<i>Stipa tenacissima.</i>
Anti-gastroentérite	06	<i>Cynara cardunculu, Teucrium polium, Globularia alypum, Rosmarinus officinalis, Artemisia herba alba.</i>
Anti-hépatite	02	<i>Asparagus acutifolius, Juniperus phoenicea.</i>
Anti-ophtalmique	02	<i>Lycium europaeum, Stipa tenacissima.</i>
Anti-ictérique	03	<i>Rhamnus alaternus, Calycotome spinosa, Juniperus phoenicea.</i>
Anti-hémorroïde	03	<i>Colocynthis vulgaris, Inula viscosa, Malva sylvestris.</i>
Anti-otalgie	03	<i>Asphodelus microcarpus, Punica granatum, Ajuga iva.</i>
Antitussif	03	<i>Pinus halepensis, Olea europaea, Allium sativum.</i>
Antibiotique	10	<i>Nerium oleandre, Globularia alypum, Calycotome spinosa, Juniperus phoenicea, Inula viscosa, Ajuga iva, Lavandula dentata, Pistacia lentiscus, Peganum harmala, Malva sylvestris.</i>
Apéritif	01	<i>Artemisia herba alba.</i>
Antalgique	04	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis, Artemisia herba alba, Marrubium vulgare.</i>
Adoucissant	01	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis.</i>
Cholagogue	01	<i>Artemisia herba alba.</i>
Carminatif	01	<i>Pimpinella anisum, Artemisia herba alba.</i>
Cardiotonique	02	<i>Ajuga iva, Juniperus phoenicea.</i>
Cicatrisant	01	<i>Salvia verbenaca.</i>
vulnérable	14	<i>Teucrium polium, Peganum harmala, Globularia alypum, Malva sylvestris, Pinus halepensis, Plantago albicans, Olea europaea, Juniperus phoenicea, Rosmarinus officinalis.</i>
Diurétique	04	<i>Pimpinella lutea, Erica arborea, Pistacia lentiscus, Ecbalium elaterium.</i>
Diaphorétique	01	<i>Pimpinella lutea.</i>
Emménagogue	05	<i>Fraxinus excelsior, Malva sylvestris, Papaver rhoeas, Salvia verbenaca.</i>
Hypoglycémiant	03	<i>Artemisia absinthium, Salvia officinalis, Rhamnus alaternus.</i>
Hypotenseur	08	<i>Marrubium vulgare, Allium sativum, Artemisia absinthium, Globularia alypum, Ajuga iva, Rosmarinus officinalis, Artemisia herba alba.</i>

Suite tableau n°6

Neuroleptique	01	<i>Chamaerops humilis.</i>
Obstique	01	<i>Marrubium vulgare.</i>
Odontalgique	05	<i>Thapsia garganica, Olea europaea, Nerium oleandre, Rosmarinus officinalis, Artemisia herba alba.</i>
Pectoral	03	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis, Peganum harmala.</i>
Stomachique	35	<i>Punica granatum, Quercus coccifera, Beta vulgaris, Malva sylvestris, Laserpitium gummiferum, Pinus halepensis, Plantago Albicans, artemisia campestris, Olea europaea, Teucrium polium, Artemisia absinthium, Salvia verbenaca, Juniperus phoenicea, Thymelaea hirsuta, Ajuga iva, Pistacia lentiscus, Quercus ilex, Marrubium vulgare.</i>
Ténifuge	01	<i>Juniperus phoenicea.</i>
Vermifuge	04	<i>Peganum harmala, Ajuga iva, Juniperus phoenicea, Rosmarinu officinalis.</i>

Tableau no 7: La liste des espèces et leurs usages

Usages	Nom scientifique
Alimentaire	<i>Allium sativum, Allium cepa, Thymus cilliatu, Allium arscalonicum, Cynara cardunculus, Triticum vulgare, Ruta gaveolens, Cicharium intybus, Salvia verbenaca, Beta vulgaris, Asparagus acutifolius, Scorzonera undulta, Ziziphus lotus, Stipa tenacissima, Borago officinalis, Quercus ilex, Olea europaea, Lauris nobilis, Origanuim glandulosum, Pistacia lentiscus, Punica granatum.</i>
Fourragère	<i>Asparagus acutifolius, Ferula communis, Calycotome spinosa, Cichorium intybus, Scorzonera undulta, Urtica pilulifera, Olea oleastre, Ziziphus lotus, Retama retam, Cynodon dactylon, Borago officinalis, Stipa tenacissima, Chamaerops humilis.</i>
Aromatique	<i>Thymus cilliatu, Salvia verbenaca, Rosmarinus officinalis, Juniperus phoenicea, Globularia alypum, Pistacia lentiscus, Origanuim glandulosum, Thapsia garganica.</i>
Toxique	<i>Globularia alypum, Nerium oleander, Thapsia garganica.</i>
Autres	<i>Amplelaudesma mauritanicum, Cynoglossum montanum, Pinus halepensis, Saponaria vaccaria, Ruta gaveolens, Peganum harmala, Ajuga iva, Nerium oleandre, Retama retam, Ziziphus lotus, Juniperus oxycedrus, Stipa tenacissima, Chamaerops humilis, Juniperus phoenicea, Pistacia lentiscus, Thymelaea hirsuta.</i>

Conclusion

Cette étude nous a permis d'inventorier les plantes médicinales utilisées dans la région d'El Haourane par le biais des enquêtes ethnobotaniques effectuées, et montre la relation étroite entre les riverains et la flore locale, cela est aperçu à travers la lecture des fiches questionnaires et on note aussi une deuxième lecture qui montre la diversification de l'usage des plantes selon plusieurs formes.

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MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND EQUIPMENTS FOR CONTROLLING THE CLIMATIC FACTORS IN WAREHOUSES FOR POTATOES

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G. BRATUCU**

Abstract: *In this paper are presented the latest generation equipments used for automatic control, monitor and climatic factors adjustment in the potatoes warehouses, equipments which have reduced energy consumption. These equipments assure optimal and constant temperature and humidity, during the storage period. The latest trends in potatoes storage combine automatic control, monitor and climatic factors adjustment with equipments which controls and adjust the atmosphere composition inside warehouses For this reason a proper management referring to the potatoes quantities which are exploited in every month is necessary. So, while sorting, the potatoes which are without injuries will be stored in cells in which exist equipments for atmospheric control but also for temperature and humidity adjustment, the rest of potatoes will be stored in cells in which exist only temperature and humidity control equipments. Another important characteristic of the modern climatic factors control and adjustment equipments is the connection of these systems through RS 485, RS 232 or USB to a process computer with an internet link. In this way the warehouse administrator will be permanently connected to the automatic equipments and he will be able to see in real time the climatic parameters inside the warehouse.*

Keywords: *automatic control, potatoes, warehouse.*

1. Introduction

The ISO 9001:1994 norms regarding Quality system accord a special attention to storing, manipulation, conservation and delivery operations through 4.15 Clause. The porpoise of this clause is to assure the consumer proper products, conforming with his requests. That is way it becomes very important the integration of storing, manipulation, packing, conservation and delivery operations through agricultural products path, not only to satisfy the consumer requests, but also for this operations to take place efficiently.

Because potatoes are perishable products, their storage requires certain conditions, which will be considerate in elaboration of the quality policy. It is recommended to avoid: stacks too heavy; natural light impact over stored potatoes; high temperatures.

Factors which determine potatoes storage necessity are:

- The technical factor which imposes the

important deliveries and making some operations which require a certain time and a special technical endowment: conditioning, packaging, labeling, marking, loading, sending, receiving;

- The economic factor- synchronizes the agricultural products input with the consume rhythm, maintains products stocks into an optimal volume for using space and assures the necessary structure for market supplying continuity with necessary products.

The potatoes nutritive value and their characteristics during the storing period must be maintained, their decrease under certain limits meaning that their introduction into the food chain is impossible.

In Table 1 are presented the potatoes main physical and chemical characteristics, which must be verified periodic during the storing [1].

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Table 1 - Potatoes physical and chemical characteristics

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Value</i>
Mass, g (limit)	30...300
Pieces/kg (limit)	3...33
Volumetric Mass, kg/m^3	650...700
Specific Heat, $Kcal/kg^{\circ}C$	0,82
Water content, %	75...80
Total sugar, %	0,40...3,40
Starch, %	12,1...20,6
Cellulose, %	0,7
Protides, %	2,00
Average content in mineral substances at 100g fresh substance, %	0,99
Carotene, mg	0,02
Vitamin B ₁ , μg	130
Vitamin B ₂ , μg	60
Vitamin PP, μg	1200
Vitamin C1, mg	20...30

In a warehouse construction an important problem is that of thermal isolation, which must assure the protection of stored products from winter frost, but also from high temperatures from the other seasons, making possible the temperature maintenance in established limits, which for potatoes are between 2... 4°C temperature and 85...90% humidity.

The materials used for warehouses cells thermal isolation (Figure 1) are: expanded polystyrene, cork, mineral felt, glass wool, polyurethane, small peeled etc.

Fig.1 Interior walls isolation

At the warehouse exterior walls (Figure 2) there can be used large panels of lightweight pre-

For avoiding vapors condensation on the warehouse cells walls there are used impermeable concentric layers, known as vapors barriers (thin foils of steel sheets, aluminum sheets, plastic material sheets, bituminous mastics etc.). In the production of isolating materials exists the tendency of realizing materials with characteristics for temperature variation isolation, but also with impermeable vapor layers. These materials contain the isolating and the impermeable material stratified

Fig.2 Exterior isolation of a warehouse

compressed concrete with both faces completely finished. Lately there were applied improved

solutions of isolated walls, through the use of aluminum edges, Koefer system, which have different cores of polystyrene. In the case of cells with controlled atmosphere the walls are sealed with metallic sheets.

In modern warehouses is adopted the bulk potatoes storage, the potatoes layer thickness being of maximum 4 m, and the surface variable in function of the ventilation and air conditioning installation capacity. As it can be observed in Figure 3, is used artificial light produced by neon tubes, which are more efficient energetically, also by not having filament they don't produce heat [3].

For adjusting climatic factors are introduced in the potatoes mass humidity and temperature sensors which transmits in real time to the process computer the potatoes mass parameters. In function of the received data from the automation system sensors there will be inserted air with optimal temperature and humidity through the perforated floor on which is placed the potatoes mass.

Fig. 3 *Specialized warehouse*

Fig.4 *Corrigo regulator*

Corrigo regulator (Figure 4) can function independent or can it can be integrated into a BMS system. Corrigo is available and without operating interface (display and keyboard). The standard Corigo E is equipped with RS 485 terminal for EXOline communication and ModBus. Optional the regulators can be equipped with port for TCP/IP or LAN. The TCP/IP variant has incorporated a Web Server. This feature makes possible the regulator integration in new or existing BMS systems and the application permanent monitoring via Internet or local computer. Connecting via LAN/Internet offers the possibility to make adjustment changes, data storing and surveillance form distance[2].

The software with which is delivered Corrigo E permits the use of a large variety of applications, being necessary just the inputs and the outputs configuration. The application dimension is limited by the regulator number of inputs and outputs. This device controls the introduced air temperature, the introduced air temperature with exterior temperature compensation, cascade control, commutation dependent on the exterior temperature between the inside temperature and the input temperature etc.

Poseidon 3468 (Figure 5) is a regulator IP with the output relay, four contact inputs without potential and four inputs for sensors. This module includes a internal web server, the outputs control and alarms through e-mails and SNMP trap. The outputs relay (at 230 V a.c.) cand be manual controlled or by a web interface.

This device alerts the operator in case of critical situation apparition (open/close contact, temperature/humidity outside imposed limits etc.). In case of an alarm, Poseidon 3468 sends an e-mail and then connects to NMS (Network Management System) through SNMP trap. The configuration and the current values indicated by sensors are accessible through the graphic interface WWW. When a contact is commutated there are send e-mails and SNMP traps to many contacts (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Poseidon regulator

To controlled atmospheres storage the equipments used for atmosphere manipulation are divided in two large categories: ones which controls the CO₂ level form warehouses known as Carbon Dioxide Scrubber (Figure 7) and the others which controls the nitrogen level (Figure 8)[5].

Also in manipulating the atmosphere using CO₂, Carbon Dioxide Scrubbers allows easy programming CO₂ concentrations for peak performance scrub and purge times, background timing defaults, CO₂ scrub cycle history, log of CO₂ levels, history of cycles per day in a room, scrubber capacity ratio and alarms. This system has a high efficiency rate because it assures a 99.9% gas purity, and manipulates the atmosphere by decreasing the CO₂ content to 2.5%.

Lately Nitrogen generators are gaining more and more field because they are an environmentally friendly substance and also a chemically non-reactive, colorless and odorless gas that comprises 79% of the Earth's atmosphere. Gaseous nitrogen is used in controlled and modified atmosphere fruits and vegetables storage and packaging to maintain the quality of fresh products by retarding oxygen-dependent ripening and decay processes. Controlled atmospheres are extensively used in the storage of apples and pears as to allow extended storage prior to sale without significant quality degradation.

Figure 6. Poseidon characteristic functions

Controlled atmosphere storage rooms for apples and pears are typically maintained at 98–99% Nitrogen concentrations with balance controlled amounts of oxygen and carbon dioxide. Nitrogen can be provided from vaporized liquid nitrogen (Figure 8), non-cryogenic generators or combustion-based generators.

Research shows that in CO₂ treated products, the removal of astringency was faster than in N₂ treated fruits and vegetables, but CO₂ treatment causes internal browning [4]. Weight loss is mainly due to losses of water through dehydration and carbon gases exchange. This weight loss is directly proportional to the gas type, its concentration and exposure duration. CO₂ application with high concentration, appreciatively 99% showed more reduction in weight loss than N₂ [4].

Conclusions

The potatoes by their complex chemical composition assures a helthy diete and are necesaty in the daily menu. Modern warehouses must be constructed with materials which assures a thermal isolation and also an effcient air vapor barrier.

For increasing the storage period there must be used regulator for constroling the climatic factors and also for manipulating the inside athmosfere.

Fig.7. CO₂ level control installation

Fig. 8. Nitrogen level control installation

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MODELLING OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PRODUCTION SYSTEM OF CURD PRODUCT

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Abstract: *the innovation strategy and the model of its technological component for the production of curd product with vegetable emulsion-type filler based on sunflower seed kernels are proposed. The model of the technological production system of the new product is developed on the basis of system approach.*

Keywords: *modelling, system approach, innovation strategy, curd product, vegetable emulsion-type filler, sunflower seed kernel*

1. Introduction

Nowadays the solution of the problems connected with the development of foods of the new type is exercised with due regard for the existing resources and limits. The output growth of semi-finished and culinary products on the curd basis has been recently observed. The present crisis in the dairy industry of Ukraine caused by the deficiency of raw milk in general and curd product in particular, negative changes in the eating habits of the population and the deficiency growth of essential nutrients bring up to date the problem of searching the alternative resources for providing restaurant business with milk raw materials and diversification of assortment at the expense of the new products with higher nutritional value [1, 2].

Under these circumstances the new products made from processed vegetable material, particularly from oil-bearing plants, having essential nutrients, play an important role [3]. The processed products made from soya, sesame, pumpkin, etc. are mainly applied as vegetable fillers in culinary production technology based on curd product. The kernels of sunflower seeds, especially those of the confectionary type, have a great reserve of functional components (protein, oil), rich chemical composition and high nutritional value [4]. In Ukraine sunflower is one of the major crops and its kernels are traditionally used either

in whole or crushed in numerous food industry technologies [4-6].

The market analysis of culinary products including sunflower kernels showed the substantial limit of their stock. Sunflower seed kernels are not used at all in the products based on curd cheese though they rank high in the human diet and are in great demand with population. The introduction of culinary technologies on the basis of curd product including sunflower kernels is limited by the insufficient level of investigation of this vegetable material.

The usage of sunflower seed kernels is preferable because their nutrients, proteins in particular, are native and possess high functional properties [7], emulsifiability being one of them [8]. Meanwhile the "refined" products of kernel processing (flour, concentrates, isolates), in spite of their improved functional properties, have lower biological protein value because of the influence of technological factors.

So the development of the scientifically supported technology for application of sunflower seed kernels and realization of various functional and technological properties of their components give the opportunity to introduce the new methods of using this vegetable resource into culinary products together with curd product. It allows developing a new class of food products possessing high nutritional value and regulated amino-acid and fatty-acid composition.

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2. Experimental part

The purpose and the tasks of the investigation

The purpose of the investigation is to create analytical foundation and to develop the technological model of curd product with vegetable emulsion-type filler based on sunflower seed kernels which can be used in culinary products.

The tasks of the investigation are as follows:

- to define the innovation strategy for the development of curd product with vegetable emulsion-type filler;
- to develop the model of technological components of the innovation strategy;
- to develop the model of the technological system for manufacturing the new product using the methods of system analysis.

Investigation conditions

To reach the objective defined and to solve the problems outlined the methods of system analysis are employed [9], different models and modelling tests being used for investigation of the systems.

While elaborating the new technological system, all the tasks are usually divided into those of analysis and synthesis. The purpose of the analysis is to divide the whole into its components and to investigate them. It simplifies the system investigated and allows representing it in its final form.

The technological system of curd production is presented as a verbal model, that is a verbal description with versatile processes characterization and the development of models of technological components both of the innovation strategy and technological system. While describing the technological system, it was important to select some subsystems so that to investigate the complex structure of the system and to range the roles of its components.

From the technological point of view we planned to elaborate the curd product, that is a semi-finished product on the basis of the low-fat curd with addition of vegetable emulsion-type filler. The latter is the product of the processed sunflower seed kernels and can be used as a component of culinary products with further adding the necessary recipe components

(vegetable and fruit fillers, flour and mélange amendments, granulated sugar, salt, etc.).

3. Results and discussions

Realization of great functional properties of kernel nutrients is possible under condition of their releasing from the whole cellular structure of the material [4-6]. So it justifies the necessity of powdering the reserve tissue of the kernels in order to maximum destroy the cells and to get the vegetable emulsion-type filler in the form of the disperse emulsifying system involving the functional properties of nutrients (protein and oil) into the technological cycle of filler production.

It should be noted that kernel coats must be removed as they have low nutritional value and phenolic compounds, which they include, decrease the biological value of protein and darken the heat-treated product [4, 6, 8].

The above-mentioned preconditions encouraged us to put forward a hypothesis according to which the usage of the low-fat curd and vegetable emulsion-type filler on the basis of the sunflower coatless kernels and lowered content of phenolic compounds makes it possible to introduce the new methods of using sunflower seed kernels and to obtain a curd product which can be used in culinary products with regulated nutrition, amino-acid and fatty-acid composition. It can be implemented under the following conditions:

- realization of functional and technological properties of kernel components in the technological process of vegetable filler production;
- ensuring high organoleptic characteristics of the vegetable filler including the light colour of the product due to lowering the amount of phenolic compounds;
- ensuring the predetermined physical and chemical, structural and mechanical, functional and technological characteristics of the vegetable filler and curd product.

Taking into account the above-mentioned, the proposed working hypothesis can be transformed into innovation strategy for the curd product development (Table 1), and as to the objective achievement – into realization of the innovation strategy components, mainly into marketing, technological, technical and organizational ones.

Table 1 Characteristics of the innovation strategy of curd product development

Innovation strategy component	Innovation requirements	Ways of innovation realization
Marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – meeting the demands of the population taking into account its various characteristics; – using the high nutritious potential of the native natural resources, both of the animal and vegetable origin; – a broad assortment of the new culinary products 	Manufacturing the curd in the form of a semi-finished product with a high degree of availability for culinary goods. It has high nutritional and biological value due to combining both animal and vegetable raw materials.
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – realization of numerous functional properties of the used raw material; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the predetermined organoleptic, physical and chemical, functional and technological, structural and mechanical characteristics of the new product; – the improved food value; – new product safety 	Removing kernel coats which are of low nutritional value and the reduction of phenolic compounds. Realization of numerous functional and technological properties of vegetable raw material components. Ensuring the long-term storage of the products under specified term and storage conditions.
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – traditional manufacturing equipment to provide stable manufacturing process 	Application of different modern technological processing methods
Organizational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – production – restaurant business, food processing enterprisers; – realization – restaurant business, supermarkets 	Introduction of organizational and technological production principles corresponding to the set tasks. Packaging, storage, transportation.

Taking into account the working hypothesis, we elaborated the model of the technological component of the innovation strategy (Figure 1) for the development of the curd product with vegetable emulsion-type filler.

The technological development of the curd product with vegetable filler on the basis of the sunflower seed kernels which are the source of valuable nutrients (protein and oil) laid the foundation of the presented model.

The amount of valuable nutrients is increased by removing the kernel coats and using the mass-transfer laws to decrease the content of phenolic compounds in sunflower seed kernels and to keep the light color of the vegetable emulsion-type filler produced on their basis. Functional properties of the kernel protein are also realized, its high emulsifying properties are ensured and the produced disperse emulsifying system is stable. The stability of the latter is achieved by means of creating structural and mechanical barrier and using the low-fat curd as a protein basis for curd product. Within the limits of the developed technical component of the

innovation strategy it is important to specify technological parameters which ensure the obtaining of the prepared cleaned kernels, the conditions of the efficient hydrothermal kernel treatment in order to decrease the content of phenolic compounds and to preserve valuable nutrients (protein and oil) in the plant cell. It is also important to ensure high organoleptic characteristics of vegetable filler and to determine conditions for obtaining its high stability. Besides, it is necessary to substantiate the product recipe and technological process for curd production.

The technological peculiarity of curd product presupposes the usage of vegetable filler based on sunflower seed kernels with removed kernel coats and the decreased content of phenolic compounds to ensure the light color of the product. To remove the coat tissue which is of little value it is necessary to use heat drying of the kernels in order to weaken the connection of the coat with cotyledon endosperm and to increase its crumbling (Figure 1, fragment 1) [10, 11].

Fig. 1. Technological component model of innovation strategy for curd product development: 1 – preparation of sunflower seed kernels, 2 – powdered kernels formation, 3 – vegetable oil emulsification and stabilization of the disperse emulsion system, 4 – obtaining curd product

The known data as to the capillary-porous structure of the reserve kernel tissue [5], the solubility of phenolic compounds in acid solutions, their ability to go through the semipermeable membranes of cell walls due to the small size of their molecules [4, 6], indifference of the water solution of acid extractant to protein and oil make it possible to apply hydrothermal kernel treatment to decrease the level of phenolic compounds in it. Meanwhile big molecules of valuable nutrients (protein and oil) do not pass through membranes and remain in the cells (Figure 1, fragment 2).

From the point of view of the hydrothermal treating the extraction of phenolic compounds from kernel tissue is a complex mass-exchange process which includes dialysis, dissolution and diffusion [12]. This process can be described by means of the mass-exchange laws according to which the diffusion of phenolic compounds increases with the increase of temperature and the dispersity of kernel parts, the concentration difference of the diffused substance between plant tissue parts and the extractant. The decrease of the extractant viscosity and the size of the molecules extracted speed up the process of diffusion too.

The process of extraction begins with the penetration of the extractant acid solution into the parts of the cell plant tissue. At first the extractant penetrates through macro- and microcracks, and then it achieves the cell through the intercellular pores and diffuses through the cell walls. While the extractant is penetrating into the cell, its content starts hydrating, swelling and enters the solution. Because of the concentration difference between substances solved in the cell and outside it, the process of the dialysis begins, that is transportation of the low-molecular substances in the reverse direction, through the cell wall, firstly into the extractant which is in the intercellular pores and then into the extractant that fills macro- and microcracks, and finally into the extractant that washes the parts of the sunflower kernel tissue. The speed of solvent penetration and substance solving is usually very high as compared with that of the internal diffusion.

Possible realization of high emulsifying properties of kernel protein in the vegetable filler technology depends on its state in the system, nativity degree, solubility, methods of material preparation, accompanying substances, salts, acids and so on. To use the protein as a surface active substance it is necessary to destroy the

plant cellular structure by kernel powdering (Figure 1, fragment 2). Taking into account the structural strength of the tissue and the size of the cells, it is necessary to apply rather intensive forces in order to achieve maximum cell destruction. The substance viscosity influences greatly this process as it determines the amount of energy needed for cell destruction and depends on the ratio of the protein, water and fatty phases in the produced disperse emulsion system.

Complex polydisperse colloidal system of the emulsion-type is produced during the process of kernel powdering. It consists of the destructed intercellular content as a disperse medium and fatty bubbles with adsorbing coatings of the surface active substances as a disperse phase. Water-soluble albumin fraction, pseudo globulins, structural lipids of organelle membranes – phospholipids – may be considered as surface active substances during the formation and stabilization of the disperse emulsion system obtained. The disperse medium is a solution of salts of mineral substances and elementary carbohydrates. It also includes suspended hard parts of the undestroyed plant tissue, cell remnants – organelles, cell coatings, insoluble swollen proteins which cannot be solved in water solution (globulins, prolamines, glutelins) and are in colloidal-disperse state.

Under these conditions the kinetic stability of the obtained disperse emulsion system is low because of the water-insoluble globulins which prevail in the fraction composition of kernel protein. This emulsion system becomes stable at the optimal ratio between water and fatty phases for a certain protein concentration used as an emulsifier. Some amount of free moisture can be bound by adding some oil which causes the appearance of the surface active substances with adsorbing coatings.

So the stability of the obtained disperse emulsion system may be purposely regulated by applying some additional amount of oil. To obtain the stable disperse emulsion system the adsorbing layers of the surface active substances, which stabilize them, must have greater structural viscosity and strength as compared with the disperse medium. These changes can be made by introducing pH acid regulators in order to approximate acid activity values to the isoelectric point of protein. It initiates certain conformational changes of protein globules and ensures the stability of the disperse emulsion system due to highly viscous, hard and spatial

structures in the surface layer, which retard the reduction of thickness and rupture of the stabilizing film on the oil bubble surface.

It is important to support the ability of the disperse emulsion system to keep its aggregative stability when being diluted, that is when low-fat curd with moisture content of 80% is added.

The model of technological system of curd production was developed on the basis of the mentioned hypothesis and technological

component of the innovation strategy (Figure 2). The data presented corroborate that the model system is given as a whole technological one within which the subsystems function in the following hierarchy: D – “Raw material preparation” → C – “Production of the powdered sunflower seed kernels” → B – “Formation of vegetable emulsion-type filler” → A – “Curd production”. Clearly-defined objectives are realized within the subsystems (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The technological system model for curd production: A, B, C, D – subsystems.

The main objective of subsystem D functioning is to get prepared sunflower seed kernels and pulped curd. Within this subsystem available native raw materials are used. They are the sources of protein and oil as functional substances.

In order to increase the content of these substances the kernel coats are removed as they have low nutritional value and high mechanical strength. So the kernels are dried and crushed. Under the mechanical effect the brittle kernel coats are separated and removed from kernels by aspiration.

To ensure the homogeneous structure and the distribution uniformity of the recipe components it is advisable to pulp the curd before mixing. It results in the formation of the disperse system with paste-like structure and creates the necessary conditions for the further even distribution of the recipe components.

During the next stage powdered kernels form the disperse emulsion system. It is realized in subsystem C. Prepared kernels are subjected to hydrothermal treatment by soaking in the solution of the pH acid regulator. It should be noted that we propose to use the citric acid solution as the pH acid regulator. It is traditionally used in restaurants and is usually available, widely-spread, safe and cheap. As a result of the process, the content of phenolic compounds decreases providing the light colour of the kernels and consequently the light colour of the vegetable filler made on their basis.

Kernels are powdered after hydrothermal treatment. During this operation great functional and technological properties of kernel components – protein and oil – which are released from the whole cell structure are realized. The result of subsystem B functioning is powdered kernel formation which is a complex polydisperse colloidal system of the emulsion type with low kinetic stability.

Subsystem B proposes step-by-step realization of such technological operations as emulsifying of the added refined deodorized vegetable oil, stabilization of the emulsion structure produced, which results in obtaining a disperse emulsion system with aggregative and kinetic stability during storage, that is the vegetable emulsion-type filler. Some amount of additional oil is introduced as its emulsification brings into proper correlation fatty, water phases and protein used as the surface active structure and increases the stability of the emulsion structure produced. The emulsion structure of the

vegetable filler is stabilized by creating structural and mechanical barrier due to application of the pH acid regulator solution and by decreasing the active acidity values of the produced system within the limits of the isoelectric point of the kernel protein.

Realization of subsystem A is the final stage of the presented model of the technological system. For this purpose low-fat pulped curd is added into vegetable filler and accurately stirred ensuring the distribution uniformity of the components and the formation of the homogeneous paste-like structure of the finished product.

The result of the functioning of the presented technological system is the development of the curd product with vegetable emulsion-type filler on the basis of sunflower seed kernels with predetermined organoleptic properties and high nutritional value which can be used as a component of semi-finished and culinary products made from low-fat curd product.

4. Conclusions

On the ground of the proposed working hypothesis the innovation strategy is presented, models of the technological component of the innovation strategy and those of the technological system of curd product manufacturing for culinary products are elaborated. The usage of the low-fat curd with vegetable filler made from sunflower seed kernels and refined, deodorized sunflower oil is considered as a basis for the product development.

It is shown that the development of the scientifically grounded technology of the vegetable filler gives the opportunity to introduce new methods of using sunflower kernels in culinary products made from the low-fat curd product which has regulated nutritional value, amino-acid and fatty-acid content.

The elaborated models (Figures 1, 2) determine strategically the necessary theoretical and experimental investigations in order to realize them in the most economically reasonable way. That is why the next investigation stage must be aimed at the necessary analytical and experimental work both within the limits of subsystems and of the technological system as a whole.

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INVESTIGATION OF PHASE TRANSFORMATION PROCESS OF HYDROACOUSTICALLY TREATED GELATINIZED CORN STARCH

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Abstract: *The results of the hydroacoustic action on the gelatinized dispersion of corn starch are considered. Gelatinized dispersion of corn starch with the set physical, chemical, functional and technological properties was produced in order to use it in the dessert production technology instead of the chemically modified starch raw materials.*

Keywords: *gelatinized starch dispersion (GSD), hydroacoustic influence, corn starch, rotary-impulse apparatus (RIA).*

1. Problem formulation

The process of GSD dispersion, i.e. destruction of its original granular structure by means of the hydroacoustic method, is the main purpose for obtaining mechanically modified corn starch which can be used in technologies of foods with unctuous or emulsion structure. As a result of our experiments we have got mechanically treated GSD with predetermined properties. It allows us to use it as a basis for dessert production which could be stored for half a year without any notable changes in its quality. We have also discovered that the process of mechanical destruction may cause undesirable technological structural changes in GSD treated gels because of the high shear stress influence.

During our investigations we have established that the influence of the hydro-acoustic field on the polymer-solvent system may initiate the original structure destruction, deformation of the new structural forms and new supramolecular structures which account for jelly formation phenomenon. Depending on the conditions of mechanical treatment, dispersion and dynamic structure formation may take place in parallel,

with or without prevailing of one process over another.

2. The purpose of investigation.

The purpose of our investigation was to study the influence of hydroacoustic RIA treatment parameters on GSD conformational and phase transformations.

3. Investigation results

Under the influence of the high shear stress, which is one of the most important components of the hydroacoustic effect on solutions and polymer gels, macromolecules unfold and orientate in the direction of the shear flow movement. It is assumed [1] that under the effect of the high shear stress and/or cavitation in the water-polymeric system the processes inverse to hydrophilic group dehydration may occur. In GSD case it may cause the formation of hydrogen bonds between dehydrated hydrophilic groups of the neighboring macromolecules orientated in a certain way and the formation of the new supramolecular structures [2, 3].

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Orientation and associative processes initiated by the high shear stress may cause the formation of the hard phase nuclei in the limiting case. Figure 1 shows the dependence of relative

optical density of GSDs with different concentrations on the treatment time in RIA.

At rather long GSD treatment with starch concentration 3...7% in RIA we observed irreversible increase of dispersion optical density.

Figure 1 – Dependence of GSD optical density on the time of hydroacoustic treatment in RIA: curves 1-7 – 1.3-8 % of corn starch - correspondingly.

The probability of forming a hard phase with the growth of starch concentration from 1 to 4% increases. With further growth of starch concentration to 8% the probability of forming a hard phase decreases. For a 9% GSD no hard phase forming has been registered.

In two-factor diagram (Fig. 2), phase transformation zone is denoted by figure 4. Solid lines within this zone characterize limiting parameters for various starch concentrations in GSD. The formation of supramolecular structures in GSD is not always accompanied with explicit changes of their optical properties.

Figure 2 – Influence of intensity and time of treatment in RIA on GSD state. Undestroyed (1), partly destroyed (2), wholly destroyed original structure (3); 4 – the zone of the hard phase nuclei formation

The indirect method of granularity evaluation also allows measuring starch reactivity in mechanically treated GSD. The effect of GSD mechanical treatment on starch reactivity was studied by means of oxidation reaction of potassium permanganate in acidic medium [4]. Rea-

gents were introduced in GSD directly after mechanical treatment. Thus, only the aftereffect of mechanical treatment was evaluated. Experimental data of kinetic measurements are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – The effect of mechanical treatment on starch reactivity in potassium permanganate oxidation reaction

Starch concentration %	K before treatment $\text{l}\cdot\text{mole}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	K_A after treatment $\text{l}\cdot\text{mole}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	K_A/K
3	$2,8\pm 0,32$	$1,8\pm 0,14$	0,64
5	$3,2\pm 0,46$	$3,1\pm 0,23$	0,97
7	$6,7\pm 0,59$	$9,3\pm 0,46$	1,59

The results obtained show that negative aftereffect of mechanical activation was observed for GSD with low starch concentration ($C < 5\%$). There was no aftereffect in the border zone ($C = 5\%$), and in the concentration zone $C > 5\%$ the starch reactivity growth was observed after treatment. One of the factors determining the reaction rate is the availability of functional groups, the hydroxyl ones in our case, which can both release during the destruction of the old structures and be involved in hydrogen bonds formation for a new structure due to changing high shear stresses during mechanical treatment. The starch reactivity decrease in the first concentration zone during mechanical treatment may be considered as a result of reduction of the available -OH groups concentration caused by the formation of the mechanically initiated associates with new intermolecular hydrogen bonds. In the second concentration zone the presence of the spatial fluctuation grid interferes with macromolecule orientation and formation of the new hydrogen bonds between dehydrated -OH groups. As a result, some growth of starch reactivity is observed in the preactivated GSD and, as a consequence, the destruction of the primary structure.

The study of the mechanical treatment effect on the starch reactivity (aftereffect) was carried out by means of variation of the intensity and the time of influence on GSD in RIA. It was es-

tablished that the influence of the mechanical effect intensity was ambiguous and the increase of the effect intensity resulted only in limited structurization. At rotor speed of 5000 rev/min, during a short-time test, starch deactivation was lower than at rotor speed of 4000 rev/min at the same time of treatment because of the associative processes. It is evident that at high intensity effect cavitation destruction of the newly-created associate occurs. As it can be seen from the presented state diagram of the mechanically broken GSD, zone 4 corresponds to the moment of nuclei formation of the hard phase and precedes zone 3 where these processes have no time for developing. It is this zone that reacts to short-time effects and presents the greatest interest for practical use because rotary-impulse apparatuses functioning at the enterprises are of the flow-through type producing a single-cycle treatment. However, as it was found out, negative structural changes might occur in this zone of the mechanical effect too.

For the first time it was established that the most characteristic consequence of the shear stress influence on the constrained dispersible systems was stress formation of the structure aftershift which manifested itself as the surface tension growth. This technologically undesirable effect worsened emulsification conditions. So it was necessary to find out all the factors that de-

terminated the level of structure stress during mechanical GSD breaking.

It should be underlined that «an after-shift stress» is not a generally accepted term. We believe this word combination to be quite allowable as it represents in the best way the effects that have not yet been described in scientific papers. These effects are initiated by the complex influence of the high shift stress and cavitation on the compound disperse liquid systems.

For low GSD concentrations (2...5%) the increment of the surface tension ($\Delta\sigma$) may be used as an aftershift stress measure. This index is determined as the surface tension disparity between mechanically and thermally broken GSD.

Figure 3 shows $\Delta\sigma$ dependence on GSD treatment conditions in RIAs of different constructions which destroy particles of the disperse phase differently having the same rotary speed.

Figure 3 – Dependence of the surface tension increment $\Delta\sigma$ (mN/m) GSD (C=4%) on the intensity n (rev/min) of mechanical treatment: 1 - rotor №1; 2 - rotor №2; 3 - rotor №3; 4 - rotor №4

On the basis of the data obtained we have made some assumptions as to the character of structural changes which result in the surface tension growth during mechanical treatment of GSD. We think that conformation of starch macro-molecules occurs during the shift stress, that they “stretch out” in the direction of the action. Linear macro-molecules of amylose dissolved in GSD water medium are mostly inclined to deformation. Macro-molecules of amylopectin having a low level of asymmetry due to their branched structure resist to shift deformation. So it is the composition of the water-soluble fraction

that plays the most important role in the process of formation of the stressed shift structure. The fraction determines the efficiency of formation of the broken granules at the given rotary speed. After termination of shift stress the system tends to equilibrium state but still there is some structure stress due to fixation of some forced deformations during treatment. During RIA treatment the stressed and deformed state of the water-soluble amylose may be fixed by the grid formation of the intermolecular bonds, associative contacts and also by the intermolecular cross-links initiated by cavitation. The data of Fig. 3 give the

assumption that the processes of formation of the polymer stressed spatial grid and its mechanical destruction take place simultaneously at the time of treatment as grid nodes are mechanically stressed and are the first to break. The decrease of $\Delta\sigma$ at the increased time treatment (Fig. 4),

and the fact that for rotors with high mechanical efficiency $\Delta\sigma$ at rotary speed of $n=5000$ rev/min is less than at $n=4000$ rev/min. (Fig. 3) prove the simultaneous mechanical destruction of the formed structural grid.

Figure 4 - Dependence of the surface tension increment $\Delta\sigma$ (mN/m) on time t (sec) of GSD mechanical treatment in RIA: curves 1, 2, 3, 4 are rotors №№ 1, 2, 3 и 4 – correspondingly

The effect of starch concentration in GSD on the surface tension change ($\Delta\sigma$) (Fig. 5) can be explained in the following way. $\Delta\sigma$ growth in the zone of low starch concentration is stipulated by the growth of the total content of the amylose dissolved in GDS. However, at concentration more than 4...4.5 % the surface tension decreases. It should be noted that the extreme value of $\Delta\sigma$ is achieved just at this starch concentration. It is at such critical starch concentration (C_{cr}) that the mechanism of viscous GSD flow changes, perhaps, because of the formation of the fluctuating physical grid. Starch concentration growth after achieving C_{cr} causes $\Delta\sigma$ decrease because of the

difficulties initiated by the shift and orientation-associative processes taking place in the system. Surface tension measurement for GSD with maximum hydrocolloid concentration is connected with methodological difficulties of its studying but it can be supposed that $\Delta\sigma$ will decrease if starch concentration increases.

Stress reversibility of the mechanically broken GSD structure is also of some interest.

It has been proved experimentally that GSD surface tension decreases again at the recurrent mechanical loads of medium intensity (stirring at 50 rev/min).

Figure 5 - Dependence of the surface tension increment $\Delta\sigma$ (mN/m) on GSD concentration C (%) during its treatment in RIA: 1 - rotor № 1; 2 - rotor № 2; 3 - rotor № 3; 4 - rotor № 4

Figure 6 - Dependence of the surface tension $\Delta\sigma$ (mN/m) of the mechanically broken GSD on relaxation time: 1- thermal breaking of GSD; 2-mechanical breaking of GSD ($t=40^{\circ}\text{C}$); 3 - mechanical breaking of GSD ($t=20^{\circ}\text{C}$)

The dependence of surface tension changes on relaxation time is presented as an example in Fig. 6.

Judging by the curves, it is evident that the shift stress of the system decreases during agitation with the magnetic stirrer and the process becomes more intensive when the temperature rises.

dessert production technology. Perhaps, it can be explained by relaxation acceleration due

The value of the surface tension of the mechanically destroyed GSD does not drop to $\Delta\sigma$ of the surface tension of the thermally broken starch. It allows defining the zones of the reversible and irreversible stress.

There was no problem caused by the increase of GSD surface tension when developing to additional mechanical stresses in the process of pumping the finished products in which we used

the starch raw material as a basis prepared in this way.

Conclusions

1. The expediency of usage of the rotor impulse apparatus for the mechanical modification of the gelatinized starch dispersion has been experimentally proved. Mechanical modification of starch takes place under the influence of the high shift stress and acoustic energy.

2. Mechanical method of GSD breaking by means of RIA allows obtaining the product with various properties. It opens up the new possibilities of its usage in dessert production technology as a thickener with low retrogradating power.

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ACCOUNTING NUANCES OF PROCEDURE OF FORMATION COST PRICE OF TOURISM PRODUCT

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Abstract: *In the article are considered theoretical and methodological aspects on formation cost price of tourist products. Is considered order of accounting reflection of preparation of tourism product. Clarified economic context of the concept of tourist products, based on the provisions of regulatory framework and research scientists. Are revealed particular qualities of creation of tourism product and calculating its cost for sale. Is assessed prospect and directions of optimization of pricing in tourism activities.*

Keywords: *tourism, tourism product, accounting, cost price, spending.*

1. Preface

Tourism is one of the leading and most dynamic branches of economy. International experts include modern tourism to field of the world economy which does not know downturns. In many countries of the world tourism played a significant role in forming of gross domestic product, creating additional workplaces and providing employment of population, stimulation of regional development, expansion of consumer market for goods and services, and stirring up of foreign trade balance. In recent years tourism has become one of most lucrative businesses in the world. Constantly is growing importance of tourism as a source of foreign exchange earnings and expansion of international relations. Tourism has a more powerful effect of multiplicator than the majority of other economic sectors.

Modern development of economy of Ukraine was initiated on the competitive market of tourist services. Stormy development of new tourism enterprises has led to fierce competition in this market. Tourism is characterized as a promising and lucrative kind of business in the world, because it needs constant attention of specialists and improvement [2].

Tourism services in the global market is compared with «invisible» product that is connected with the specifics of tourism consumption, which occurs in places production of tourist services.

The existing accounting methodology does not fully is focused on cost management of enterprises of tourism industry, that causes complications in optimizing economic situation

of national tourism industry and economy as a whole. In this aspect relevant is direction of research at deepening theoretical and methodological basics of accounting of costs and analysis of cost price of tourism product.

2. Economic and legal tools of definition of tourism product

Any product is a carrier of various specific of properties that reflect its usefulness and meeting certain needs and requirements. Usefulness of the product determines its consumer cost, which, in turn, should be evaluated, that is to say is to be determined its quality.

According to the Law of Ukraine «On tourism» tourism product – is a pre developed complex of tourism services, which combines no less than two such services that is implemented or offered for sale at specified price, which consists of services of transportation, services of accommodation and other tourist services not related to transportation and accommodation (services for the organization visits to objects of culture, recreation and entertainment, sales souvenir production, etc.) [12].

Domestic researchers define tourism product as ordered set of tourism services, works and goods (package of tourism services), which consists of a minimum of two or more single or multiple tourism services, works, goods and means of ensuring, other tourism resources that sufficient to meet the needs of tourists in the process and the purpose of tourism [10].

In the consumer market tourism product acts as a set of tangible and intangible benefits that

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are required to service set of specific tourist routes. Complex of such benefits, which formed to meet the needs of tourists on a separate route has holistic target character, called package of tourism products and services at the market as a commodity unit.

The main difference tourism product from tourism service is that the service can be bought and consumed at the place of production. Tourism products can be purchased the place of residence, but consume only in place production of tourism services [1].

Tourism product – concept a comprehensive, which is formed from of many interconnected components – tourism services. Tourism product includes not only tourism services, but also additional tourist-excursion services and products, that is, those, are not provided permit and transmitted to consumer in the mode its free choice [5].

Tourism product is same subject of contractual relationship just like any other product offered to consumption. Nevertheless should take into account its specific characteristic traits, namely: variability of quality, territorial delineation of service providers, their sellers and customers; lifecycle, rapid loss of consumer qualities; information richness, a high degree of individualization, multiplier effect of consumption tourism services.

Failure to store, impossibility of their accumulate, as goods, enhances entrepreneurial risk in Tourism. As a consequence unrealized tourism product, including services of hotel, transport, excursion service, are not implemented for reasons of seasonality or other nature, leads to spending.

3. Composition and structure of tourism services

One of the characteristic of features of tourism services is inseparability of their production and consumption. Service can be provide only when the received an order or has appeared client.

Tourism activity does not share production, sale, consumption of services either in time or in space. Consequently, production, sales, consumption of tourism services occurs simultaneously, not standing out in separate stages.

Proposed tourism services that comprehensive make up tourism product, researchers on the issues of organization and

implementation of tourism business is classified into different categories (fig. 1.) [6- 9, 14, 16].

For accounting and taxation of operations which are carried out by economic entities in the sphere of tourism activities, important that proposed tourism products is complex of services (not goods), that motivates use in accounting and tax accounting rules established by regulatory legal acts for services [15].

Main object of accounting production (formation) and the implementation of a range of tourism services are financial resources, which nested to components of tourism products. To obtaining the necessary information for the management it is imperative to form of accounting and analytical information about the value of resources in producing of tourism products. In accounting envisages forming of prime cost of tourism services on account of «Production».

Prime cost the proposed product is defined as cost estimate of material and immaterial character that were used in the production (formation) and implementation of tourism products. In this aspect it is imperative determine the composition of the finished product, which form the final cost.

At the implementation order are offer the primary unit of tourism products - tour which under the current legislation is defined as a tourist trip (trip) according to the established route within the specified period, that ensured comprehensive set of tourism services for comfortable stay and meet the needs to rest (lodging, meals, transportation). Additionally, by mutual consent, as part of the tour may be included also other services that are not associated with accommodation and transportation – services in organization of visits to objects of culture, recreation, entertainment, sale of souvenir production, etc. Standard composition of tour should include positions regarding comfortable stay of tourist in place of rest (tab. 1).

Fig. 1. Typical services that make up the tourism product

Table 1 - Components of standard tour

Tourism service	On the choice of the customer (or depending on tour)
Transportation	Air flight - indicate information about airline and aircraft, which carry out flight, to the official site of subject of tourism Railway transport - indicate information about number and class train carriage Bus transportations - indicate information about partner carrier (e-mail)
Transfer	In fixed price includes: - organized a meeting at the train station at the airport or available from submission holding a sign; - text on the rating plate tend to determines client; - client expectations during the hour after aircraft landing or arrival of the train; - waiting during 15 minutes in place of location (except for airports and train stations); - free mobile communication with driver. Type of group transfer: group, individual, VIP-transfer
Accommodation and catering	Accommodation is provided in accordance with reserved category of hotel (star) and confirmed by type of room specified in travel voucher. Food options: Bed and Breakfast (BB) – only breakfast Half Board (HB) – breakfast and dinner (dinner and drinks throughout the day - extra charge) Full Board (FB) – Breakfast, lunch and dinner (drinks for lunch, dinner and during the day - extra charge) All Inclusive (AI) – full board basis: breakfast, lunch and dinner (soft and alcoholic local drinks during the day - free) Super, Excellent, Ultra, High Class All Inclusive, Royal AI – species All Inclusive, under which depending on the hotel are offered additional free services (for example alcoholic beverages imported) Provided for in standard rooms provision of additional bed for children (up to three beds in the room). Form of service: «A la carte» offers customers free choice of dishes from the restaurant menu «Table d'hote» provides a single menu for all customers without the right choice «Buffet» self-service and free choice of dishes of the proposed
Insurance	Insurance policy from company partner. Standard insurance policy includes insurance medical and travel expenses and insurance against accidents. By insurance contract provides for unconditional franchise - part of the losses, which is paid independently and not reimbursed by the insurance company. Standard policy does not cover the costs of treating injuries that have occurred as a result of diving, rafting, motosafari, horseback riding and other outdoor activities. Polis should provide for noctidial information and legal support
Legal assistance	In the event of wrongful case that infringes legitimate interests of tourists, he can at any time apply to the representative of International Bar Association «Defense League» and get qualified advice, council of legal questions, reference information under the legislation of the country of temporary stay, protection in civil cases of administrative offenses, criminal cases (except for the protection of consumer rights), in which the tourist passes as a plaintiff / defendant, suspect, accused, victim. For organization legal assistance tourist should contact with representative of insurance company by phone specified in the policy
Leisure	Excursions and walks, sports and wellness services that are included in the tour price
Visa	Includes payment of consular fees
Mandatory extra charge	Surcharges that are associated with a comfortable staying on trips
Additional surcharge (at pleasure)	Visiting the excursion sites (if not included in tour price)

4. Pricing in the tourism business

From 3 August 2012 in Ukraine there is new Law «On Prices and Pricing», which regulates the procedure price formation domestic economic entities [13]. Among altered notions should be allocated the notion of prices. Previously, the notion of prices has been enshrined in economic Code of Ukraine, according to which price has been defined as a form of monetary expression of cost of goods (works, services), which realize subjects of management [3]. At present price is defined as expressed in monetary form equivalent of unit of the commodity (products and services, material and technical resources, economic and moral rights), which must be applied as tariff, size of payment, rate or gathering, other than rates and charges that are applied in taxation system [13]. Stipulation about price is material to economic contracts, so change that was introduced is extremely important for economic entities, since the lack conditions in economic contract theoretically may be regarded as grounds for the recognition the contract not concluded. Structure of prices of tourism product includes the following main elements: cost price, profit, discounts and allowance.

Formation of the price for the services of tourism takes place on two levels [14]. First level determines pricing strategy. It manifested through a set price, which due to be published in catalogs, and brochures, guidebooks and other special publications. These prices relate to questions of positioning of services and goods, their cost, long-term income on invested capital as well as prospects of development industry, position on the market. At the second level price formation reflects formation of prices sales in the period ahead. Prices vary in process of implementing depending on the time of production of tourism product, and also at booking tickets prior to the trip.

Price on tourism services has two boundaries: lower and upper. Lower limit is cost price of manufactured item (of tourist product), and the upper limit is determined by the demand for the given goods. From this we can determine that the magnitude of prices of tourism product is determined by its value and demand for this product. Additionally on the price of tourism product influenced by a number of factors: class of service, vehicle, form of maintenance (group

or individual), conjuncture of market of tourism services, seasonality provision of services, effectiveness of advertising, etc.

5. Calculation and an accounting reflection costs of formation of cost price of tourism product

Prime cost of tourism product – is value of material and other expenses that are used in the production and sale tourism product, and other costs for its promotion and implementing. Cost price of realized tourism product consists of the production cost of production, which has been implemented during the reporting period, undistributed constant general production expenses and above permitted production costs. Prime cost to create tourism product consists only of the current costs of tourism firms.

Structure of expenditures changes depending on the country of stay, group of tourists, their purchasing power, range, quality of services and scale of activities of the organization.

Costs that form production cost of tourism products, include costs are directly related to its creation, which are carried out accordance with the provisions Law of Ukraine «On tourism» and thesis (standard) accounting 16 «Expenses» [11, 12]:

- direct material costs include: costs of acquisition (production) services in transportation, temporary accommodation, meals, excursion, health resort, sport, entertainment and other service of tourists, as well as providing typical and accompanying tourism services;
- direct labor costs of, in particular labor costs of workers employed creating, promoting and selling tourism product;
- other direct costs: charges on wages, rents (retention) premises, depreciation of fixed asset objects and intangible assets;
- constant general production expenses that remain unchanged when changing the volume of activity tourism enterprises: costs of communal services, safety, labor safety;
- variables general production expenses that vary proportionately to change of volumes activity of the company: costs of official business trip, wages and relevant charges on wages administrative staff.

The list of and composition of articles of calculations of production cost price of tourism product and well as a list of and composition of variable and fixed general production expenses are established enterprise.

Calculate the cost of tourism products carried out first by primary activity, that is according to the package of services on a group of tourists in the whole, and then determined by the cost price calculating per one tourist and is set price of services. After total price is adjusted for the amount of the proposed discount which is determined in accordance decision of the subject of provision of tourism services. If the product is realized through travel agent, additionally need to calculate and to lay in price of tourism products remuneration for travel agent.

Activities of travel agencies is to advance the and implement of tourism products that formed the tour operator. Activity of travel agents performed on the basis agreements of commission, powers of attorney or agency agreements. It was from kind of contract (agreement) depends on the way you view operating expenses in the accounting and tax accounting. The agreement may be enclosed with: tourists (to purchase vouchers), operators (vouchers for sale) other travel agent (for sale or purchase of vouchers).

Travel agent organizes its activities in accordance agreements of commission and agency agreements. Income consists of sum of commission, which is set fixed amount or as a percentage of cost of tourism products.

The costs of implementation of tourism products or services intermediaries (travel agents) differ from the costs of their formation. They are calculated similarly to costs in retail trade and covered on sum of commission. Costs of travel agents by implementation of tourism products contain virtually no material costs. The main type of cost of these enterprises are labor costs of and relevant charges on wages [4].

Procedure of accounting of general production expenses on accounts of determined by the accounting policy of enterprise. Accounting policies of the subject tourism activities should determine account of accounting of general production expenses, procedure of their allocation and writing off at the end of reporting period.

For accounting cost price of tourism products are used active accounts: «Production», «General production expenses». On the accounts «Administrative expenses», «Expenditure on marketing», «Other operating expenses» reflect the costs associated with the economic activity of tourism enterprise.

Amount of revenues by tourism services are taken into account under account «Subtractions

from income». At the end of reporting period received income and expenses incurred are debited to the account «Results from operating activities».

Reducing the costs associated with forming and promotion of tourism products is the basis of price reduction, and also has an impact on reducing costs in other branches of economy. Of great importance is reduction costs and to reduction the need for circulating assets, videlicet exists necessity of carrying out systematic control by decline of expenses on formation and implementation of tourism products.

Reserves of reducing cost price is cost elements associated with the formation and implementation of tourism products. Travel firm can only affect internal factors therefore common sources of lower prices for tour product is to reduce material costs, amortization charges, reduction of administrative costs and expenditures on salary of. Among external factors that reduce the price of products offered, is allocated seasonality that allows to offer tourism product to consumer at a reduced price.

Nevertheless among of customer audience for the most part dominated by the desire to get of full value service in season even with higher price.

Conclusions

A key object of attention of accounting process is the formation of tourism product, namely, material and other costs that are committed at the production, promotion and its implementation.

Great influence on price formation in the tourism industry has government, which through various means can regulate prices for tourism products.

Investigating the issue of price expression on formation of tourist products, one can argue, that extraordinary importance is the question on improvement methodology of calculation of production cost tourism services. Is equally important optimize expenses that indirectly related to the production and promotion of the product to the consumer. It is necessary to rank the costs associated with the production of tourism products, depending on the economic expediency and their financial justification.

Otherwise quite hard to control prices that logically lead to loss of customer audience. Additionally necessary take into account fact that cost of newly created product will be vary

significantly from already formed. Nevertheless, travel enterprise often ignore this important aspect and offer a single price for of tourism products. Price policy of today is extremely important for development of tourist business.

The high level of competition in the tourism market, the development of individual tourism without intermediaries, the unsettled prices and quality of the proposal requiring as soon as possible resolving the issue of calculating the cost price of the finished product that offered for sale. Is quite possible is submitted development of the sector of e-commerce, namely subjects of distance selling which offer tourism services.

This will reduce the size of administrative costs that significantly will affect concernment of potential customers. The question arises on consumer protection, but taking a into consideration norms of domestic law, acquired experience e-commerce, development of the information society, can say that this organizational form fully has meet the expectations of sellers and consumers of tourism products that are constantly in discussion relations regarding the prices of.

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A PRINCIPAL MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF OBJECT CRUSHING AT IMPACT MILLS

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Abstract: *The paper presents an original mathematical model for describing the model of object crushing at impact mills. The mathematical model of a to-be-ground object flow, that had deduced previously, allows obtaining an insight into both to-be-ground objects and their multitude and their movements before and after grinding. Crushing the mass of to-be-ground objects is reasonable to be characterizing by distributions of the values of the said factors and the number of to-be-ground objects' fragments. It is reasonable to distinguish the distribution of those factors from among them, which correspond to to-be-ground objects with the given characteristics – given mass, given linear size etc. With that, it is sufficient to take only those distributions that correspond to the given interval values of the to-be-ground objects' masses.*

Keywords: *mathematical model, crushing, impact mills.*

1. Introduction

One of the main tasks of the food and process industry is to comprehensively use raw materials varying in nature, structural and rheological features such as nuts, cacao, cacao butter, sugar, grains etc. It is worth noting that there have been many studies concerning the processing of such materials both abroad and in the post-Soviet countries.

According to the generally accepted classification, the processes of producing sugar powder, crushed cacao, grinding other friable masses in the food industry is referred to fine and ultrafine crushing and achieving the standard dispersity requires much power inputs [1, 2, 3].

Therefore, reducing the power costs for the process, especially with regard to fine and ultrafine crushing is the most important scientific and technical problem. Reducing the energy intensity while intensifying the process can be achieved only provided that the crushing process parameters and the crushing design parameters are efficiently balanced. A task like this can be scientifically solved through multifactorial mathematical modeling of a specifically considered crushing process. The obtained mathematical model serves as grounds for

solving engineering optimization tasks, the ones of effectively selecting the main crushing process's technological and technical parameters and crushers [4, 5].

Moreover, an impact whose effectiveness depends on what effective modes are selected causes forces to appear that increase and decrease within a short period of time. At that, there appear stress waves in both the working element and the deforming environment, which, at certain intensity, facilitate the forming of an advance crack [2, 3].

2. New approaches about crushing process

In this connection, vibrating as a method of intensifying workflows has started to be widely applied in the food industry. For example, different kinds of vibrating equipment that are remarkable for their high performance are more and more used at food industry enterprises.

Using vibrating impact elements in crushers allows intensifying the process of destructing the crushed materials particles, reducing raw material losses, improving the separated surfaces quality and reducing the

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cutting efforts. However, some issues constituting the problem's physics and being of absolute practical interest and, in particular, issues of defining the optimum vibrating cutting efforts are not studied enough yet, which causes much difficulties calculating and selecting the optimum parameters of the vibrating crushing equipment's impact cutting units.

The well known fundamental crushing theories [1, 2, 3] place special emphasis on identifying the dependence of energy on the ratio of size reduction. Not denying the principal importance of this issue, let us note that such theoretical description of this process is incomplete. This incompleteness mostly manifests itself in the fact that, with this approach, a process's non-power regularities such as the dependence of ratios of size reduction on crushed product's physical properties and the crusher's design characteristics and crushing method are not applied. Besides, crushing is characterized not only by changing the to-be-crushed object's biggest linear size, but also changing its shape, mass and other characteristics.

For the mentioned reasons the article considers in more details the crushing of to-be-ground objects. It's says that individual crushing steps are distinguished, the number of the relevant characteristics of to-be-ground objects increases and the probabilistic approach to the process description is assumed as a basis. This approach was previously used in the other investigations.

The mathematical model of a to-be-ground object flow, which we have deduced previously [5], allows obtaining an insight

into both to-be-ground objects and their multitude and their movements before and after grinding. In addition, this model does not describe the conversion of an input flow into an output flow due to the fragmentation of moving objects. Therefore, this article consider the object crushing model that, together with the previously obtained mathematical model, forms a common mathematical model of the ordered collection of crushing processes in the gradual crushing mill.

In impact crushers (for example, a hammer mill, a disintegrator, and a dismembrator) objects start to be crushed once to-be-ground objects contact the crusher's working element (a hammer, a wall, or both). The to-be-ground object is crushed very quickly – for fractions of a second. During this time a whole to-be-ground object is broken up into the known number of parts.

Subject to the to-be-ground object's properties, state, collision conditions and intensity the number of fragments (particles) of the to-be-ground object may vary. Due to the probabilistic nature of crushing the number of fragments is a random value. The random values of crushing include mass (m) of a i -th fragment (particle) and its geometrical characteristics – linear dimensions (l), surface area (S) and volume (V).

In fact, crushing is characterized completely enough by the relation of the appropriate characteristics of the obtained fragments and the appropriate to-be-ground object. It concerns the relations such as:

$$\frac{m_1^i}{m}, \frac{l_1^i}{L_1}, \frac{l_2^i}{L_2}, \frac{l_3^i}{L_3}, \frac{S_1}{S}, \frac{V_1}{V} \quad (1)$$

In this connection, the crushing of a single to-be-ground object is reasonable to

characterize by the set of ratios of size reduction:

$$k_1 = \frac{m_1^i}{m}, k_1^i = \frac{l_1^i}{L_1}, k_2^i = \frac{l_2^i}{L_2}, k_3^i = \frac{l_3^i}{L_3}, k_s^i = \frac{S_1}{S}, \dots \quad (2)$$

Crushing the mass of to-be-ground objects is reasonable to characterize by distributions of the values of the said factors and the number of to-be-ground objects' fragments. There are many distributions like these. It is reasonable to distinguish the distribution of those factors from among them, which correspond to to-be-ground objects with the given characteristics – given mass, given linear size etc. This way, there appear a great number of distributions. With that, it is sufficient to take only those distributions that correspond to the given interval values of the to-be-ground objects' masses.

Assume that the symbol m_u designates the minimum and the symbol m_a the maximum mass of all to-be-ground objects. In this case the interval (m_u, m_a) is broken into n parts with a value of $h = \frac{m_a - m_u}{n}$.

Further, for each interval $[m_u + (i-1)h; m_u + ih]$ there are considered the functions of distribution $F_m(x)$, $F_a(x)$, $F_b(x)$, $F_c(x)$, $F_s(x)$ and $F_v(x)$ of the values of factors of corresponding classifications of parts (particles) crushed by their masses, linear sizes, areas and volumes.

This concerns the following functions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} F_m^j(x) &= P(K_m^j < x) \\ F_a^j(x) &= P(K_a^j < x) \\ F_b^j(x) &= P(K_b^j < x) \\ F_c^j(x) &= P(K_c^j < x) \\ F_s^j(x) &= P(K_s^j < x) \\ F_v^j(x) &= P(K_v^j < x) \end{aligned} \right\} (3)$$

where j – interval number ; K_m^j – ratio of size reduction by mass; K_a^j – ratio of size

reduction by length; K_b^j – ratio of size reduction by width; K_c^j – ratio of size reduction by height; K_s^j – ratio of size reduction by surface area; K_v^j – ratio of size reduction by volume.

The set of the said ratios of size reduction (2) together with the functions (3) give a full idea on crushing. Therefore, this set is called a mathematical model of one-step crushing.

A multistep crushing description requires attracting the said sets of distribution functions in a number equal to that of crushing steps. In this connection, the collections of the said sets of the given fields of 3D space, ratios of size reduction and distribution functions are considered as a mathematical model of multistep crushing.

Therefore, it is worth stating that a pile-up (complication) of distribution functions is of little use to put them in practice. For this reason, the proposed model is further discussed in languages of the characteristics of random values such as mathematical expectancy, dispersion, median etc.

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STUDY REGARDING ATTRACTIVENESS OF MOUNTAIN ZONE

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Abstract: *There is approached the extremely preoccupying problem of Europe mountains and, especially, of the Carpathian Mountains, focused on the perspective of mountain attractiveness. The paper analyses this direction and tries to solve certain aspects concerning the sustainable development of this zone. Thus there are underlined a series of possibilities with an important potential of attractiveness for the mountain zone. It is described the transition from the concentrated model to the diffuse and multiform model, capable to stimulate the attractiveness of the zone of high and medium altitude. There are enumerated several pragmatic methods, as well as the application strategy, with the description of a subprogram of mountain development for the Carpathian Mountains from Romania. It is described too the project proposed at the European Congress of the Mountain in France from October 2013, European cooperation project for the consolidation of Alps-Carpathians integrate development on the "eco-agro-touristic" axes, by biodiversity capitalization, of agro-zoo technical production and of traditional gastronomy. Propositions are made regarding the elaboration of a Common Mountain Policy at European level.*

Keywords: *mountain, attractiveness, model of development, European policy of the mountain, mountain research project.*

1. Introduction

In actual vision, the mountain is perceived as a unitary territory (routs, houses, products, scenery etc.) in a dynamic economy. They are all the time building, in the European mountains, based on a collective labor, having as a result the synergy of actions necessary to the development of the fragile mountain zone. The successful models from certain mountain ranges of Europe constitute reference points for the mountain zones with problems of different gravities. But on the whole, mountain attractiveness being in sufferance, it becomes opportune that, at European level, the mountain development becomes a prior preoccupation for the decades to come [5,10]. Climate, social and economic changes impose in fact the capitalization of this huge reserve, given by the European mountain potential and, first of all, by the European "spine" represented by the Alpine-Carpathian geosynclinals.

The mountain agro-food economy must be treated very attentively, in direct correlation with

the effects of accelerated demographic growth, of the recession of alimentary crises at world level and of the importance of predictable climate changes by which will be reduced agricultural surfaces, beginning with hillside zones and even beyond these ones [2,8,9]. Thus, there where there are mountains with traditions in food production, their role is in the even more intense growth and the degradation phenomena should be stopped, emerging the logical, objective and urgent necessity to act in favor of sustainable agricultural and rural development - **distinctly specific to the mountain zones.**

A basic strategy sustains the pronounced diversification of technical and economic activities in the mountain zones. There is taken account of making mountain agro-zoo technical products, developing quality in food industry, but also capitalizing resources specific to each massive separately: hydropower centrals, granite industry, textile industry, wood industry, tourism industry, small artisan industry and others, where necessary. In order to increase a sustainable and efficient mountain economy, it is extremely important the idea of administrative decentralization based on specific technostuctures. At the same time, the attractiveness of

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the mountain zone must be directly linked to the tourist economy [3,4,7].

Mountain ranges are a space especially centered on attractiveness. The forest and the environment in general constitute a patrimony that must be conserved and developed. The mountain scenery will be practically adapted to economic modernization. But all these not at random, but professionally, taking into account the specific of the mountain zone (for example the modern houses, completed with wooden roof framing, with balconies and wooden staircases, etc.). We mean thus the increase of diversity, putting into value the mountain resources and responsibility towards mountain scenery and towards future.

It is not easy to define attractiveness, as well as it is not easy to find the best solutions to be applied. Nevertheless, as poles of mountain attractiveness there are considered **the mountain resorts**. The core of attractiveness is represented by strong resorts, of residential attractiveness and especially of attractiveness by evidence of original resources, specific to the respective mountain territory [1,6].

It must be mentioned that mountain ranges have different attractiveness, so that there are hyperactive territories and little attractive territories.

2. Work Methodology

The applied managerial techniques will have to answer the question: Which is the attractiveness model of the "X" mountain zone? And the attractiveness model of mountain tourism? What place does mountain tourism occupy in comparison to other types and forms of tourism in different European countries? For example, in France mountain tourism is the 3rd tourism, even though it has been lost approximately 5 % from its frequentation during the last 5 years in several mountain ranges.

The applied sociological methodology puts into evidence as threats:

- the things related to UE policy in relation to the mountain
- how there may be constructed a synergy between the mountain ranges
- how to solve situations linked to the resources with problems.

As opportunities:

- the development of a new mountain population, especially in order to methodologically educate in the modern spirit, i.e. profoundly professional, the youth from the mountain zone.

3. Results and Discussions

It is known that in the mountains life is very different from many point of view, so that tourism too is different from the seaside tourism, but nearer to the urban tourism. The specific of the agro-forest-pastoral and rural space of the zones with medium and high altitude presupposes, especially for the future, a boosting of the development of the mountain territory:

- receiving policy combined with general touristic policy
- specific marketing
- brand and label
- diversification of economic activity and construction of multi transversality type by the link between the mountain economic and social systems.

As basis of activity, **agriculture and mountain tourism** are *de facto* the main elements of attractiveness. From all that has been briefly presented it is fully demonstrated as an objective request to take efficient measures through which to fight against tendencies of agricultural abandon and excessive migration of the youth from the mountain rural. The need of the existence of a good organization and of certain distinct agro-rural policies, specialized for the mountain specificity is an acute and permanent request for a large economic-social European segment and for the insurance of an EQUILIBRIUM in the economy and society of the UE states. Thus it may be assured a **basis of renewable resources** of inestimable value in the mountain zone. More than that, genuine agriculture-breeders of mountain animals are the unique depositors of extremely valuable agro-economic and cultural-spiritual traditions, i.e. a treasure of the European Union nations [9].

Unfortunately, not very rarely, it appears a gap between the mountain imaginary and reality, as for example the situations when tourists come to the mountain for Nature and fresh air and find ATVs and pollution. The complex problems, some of which have been described, impose the definition of a model of development and increase of mountain attractiveness (table 1).

Table 1 STIMULATION OF ATTRACTIVENESS OF EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN ZONE

Consecrated model <i>(concentrated model)</i>	New model <i>(diffuse-multiform model)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - model of integrated resort (ex. resort of mountain sports); - model of small mountain places for skiing, with architecture attractive for the eye, with "a plus of Nature", i.e. local materials (wood etc.); - model of mixed economy where public power together with private one interferes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - multiform practices / diversity / rethought in the new model from economic, cultural, environment, spiritual point of view; - new contacts / meeting rooms; - model that is spontaneously constructed; - comfortable flats in non altered environment; - identification and capitalization of cultural patrimony of the respective territory; - the model differs in relation to altitude; - economic model of local inter communities: the power of private ones in investments; qualification of private initiative including through inter comminatory projects; creation of private organizations which invest in infrastructure and in extra season programs (high quality, exclusivist investments, places where people may spend money all over the year etc.); - local network - all the local actors to pilot projects in order to save expenses in the mountain area; it is taken as granted that local communities are extremely imaginative, as well as the contributive capacity of the local inhabitants; - in tourism - social expenses are to be found in this model (ex. capitalization of women's labor from the community or the casuals' one etc.); - professional specialization towards seasonality (to take into account what the market is demanding as for the seasonality - ex. integration of seasonal 4 star locations); promotion of local territory through marketing actions (products from the territory, network of shops with local products etc.); - decentralized and pragmatic education: "snow classes" for the youth to learn how to ski (missing one children generation without knowing how to ski has irreparable consequences for health and sport development); sportive education - the youth to learn how to skate, action that will make skating rinks profitable; - mountain attractiveness through actions of health reestablishment (medical cabinets / clinics / balneal tourism etc.)

3.1. Pragmatic measures concerning the new model of mountain development

Transition towards the diffuse model aims to bring more money in the system. Maybe the best solution is the models' complementarity and not reciprocal exclusion, but also with adaptation to the future conditions and fixing certain rules and principles. Among the principles of the new model comes out the idea of: "selling the territory's culture to the territory's population, in order to transmit it further to the tourists", or there is asked a basic question: "does the

territory make the resort, or the resort makes the territory" ?

As an important rule, we mention conserving and, at the same time, developing the local patrimony. This complex action also presupposes to find optimal promotion elements (for example, commune elements: green economy / traditional economy / renewable energy etc. in relation with green tourism); also, to find social solutions for demographic balance between rural and urban.

As important measures linked to the development of the mountain zone, as a fragile zone, we briefly put into evidence the following aspects [7,10]:

- the mountain to be sustained by the other regions, more developed;

- to legally stipulate the rights of the mountain population (rights on underprivileged geographic zones and not on obsolete and no-economic criteria of the ethnic, racial, religious, etc. type);
- environment policy especially for the mountain zone (for example the mountain sustains with water the other regions, therefore, in order to maintain economic difficulties from the mountain zone, to extra pay water and hydro energy by the other regions - different bills tax in town/ tax in the mountains etc.);
- micro regional strategies (school and university education, implication of research and science in mountain economy, as for example formation of tens of thousands of ski monitors / promotion of events, of fairs and exhibitions for mountain production, network of shops with territory products etc.)

3.2. Stimulation of mountain attractiveness in the Carpathians from Romania

Pragmatically regarding the things, it becomes necessary to put into evidence the themes of the *Subprogram for the mountain zone from Romania: 2014-2020*. Its main components refer to [9]:

- Themes on MOUNTAIN ENVIRONMENT direction
- Themes on direction of optimal management of the AGRO-FOREST MOUNTAIN zone
- Themes on LEGISLATIVE AND INSTITUTIONAL direction
- Themes on direction of CULTURAL IDENTITY OF THE MOUNTAIN ZONE.

In order to implement programs aiming to mountain attractiveness, it is essential the existence of a high professional quality human resource. Thus it becomes opportune to briefly analyze the **specificity of problems linked to human resources in the mountain zone** [9]:

- Justification of renewing the mountain human resource also derives from the specific role the mountain farmers play as „environment carers” and conservers of good practices and valuable cultural traditions.

- There are no other reasonable solutions that may replace mountain farms and farmers. The European and worldwide experience has shown that mountain populations, once having left the mountains, cannot be brought back, and solutions

to replace them do not exist (urban or rural populations, from the plain, cannot manage in the mountain agro-zootechny, not only physically and psychically, but also from the point of view of specific competence and abilities).

- Through sustainable development of the mountain agro-zoo technical and rural economy, through tourism, small industries and other positive externalities from Romania's Carpathians (as there are also in the mountains of other emergent countries from EU), the mountain economy may become a major and long lasting contributor to the economic-social equilibrium from Romania and, implicitly, from the European Union.

- The mountain population is the guarantor of the fact that mountain agro alimentary products are of high quality, especially ecological, and by rural tourism and agro tourism - the mountain contributes to the health estate of the urban population and to the reduction of health expenses.

- The existence in Romania of an experience, of certain important accumulations (1990-2013) of knowledge and interpretation, as well as of an institutional experience, but also results from research and innovation, work models, nongovernmental organizations, initiatives in education, specific legal frame (the Strategy of sustainable development of the mountain zone and the Mountain Law - the third law of the mountain in EU, after Italy and France) and an official delimitation of the mountain zone, constitute an advantage which has been created with big efforts, that is necessary to be reactivated, consolidated and developed. All these with the necessary support (financial and organizational) and in realistic, possible steps, by selecting priorities and emergences, by correcting errors and perseverant pursuit of certain growth and stability objectives, under the limits that the mountain environment sustainably bears.

Also, under the context of the process of administrative-territorial reorganization, it becomes opportune to take into consideration the model of „regional and interregional policy at the level of mountain ranges” (applied in France), as well as the creation of certain „mountain districts” at intercommoned level, on traditional micro zones. These ones may be assigned to Regional Mountain Stations at European level, if in the future the European Commune Mountain Policy will develop. All these presuppose the existence of special prepared people for mountain regionalization.

➤ PROPOSITION OF PROJECT ON FINANCE PROGRAM 2014 - 2020

Premises

As for the Carpathian Basin and the large arch of the Carpathian Mountains from the Romanian territory, at the same time as the actual modernity, it paradoxically is registered a low dynamics of development and even a leaving of the mountain zones. It is unacceptable that, 2000 years after (since the Thracians, Dacians and Romans), period in which these mountains have been the spine of Romanians' development and resistance against time vicissitudes, to observe a real *social desertification* during the last decades. It is extremely important, not to miss mountain life continuity, to imagine projects that bring back people to mountain zones. Concerning Romania, we consider extremely useful to offer viable and attractive projects in order to bring home an important part of those who have emigrated in different European countries.

That is why the common effort of specialists in mountain development from Europe, through such integrated projects, is more valuable by its social dimension, together with the economic and ecologic ones. It is necessary an **European common mountain policy!**

To concretize what has been mentioned, it is realistic to propose a concrete research direction, context in which we propose a project of European cooperation for the mountain zone:

Theme of principle of the project:

Increase of mountain zone attractiveness and consolidation of integrated development of Alps-Carpathians on the axe "eco-agro-touristic", by capitalization of biodiversity, of agro-zoo technical production and of traditional gastronomy.

Conserving biodiversity (still well represented in the Carpathian Mountains), but also its optimal capitalizing, concomitantly with sustainable development of mountain agriculture (better represented in the Alps Mountains), may constitute the basis of creating an ***integrated model of European mountain development***.

The existence of a large **consortium** makes possible a synergy of common experience, which, by avoiding up to now errors, may also lay the conceptual basis of a strategy of practical action in order to remediate problems linked to biodiversity, to mountain agriculture and to their capitalization through a responsible ecotourism and agro tourism.

We mention that Transylvania University from Brasov (i.e. from the largest town inside the whole chain of the Carpathian Mountains), respectively through the Research Centre *EBIOTEFA*, together with the Centre for Biodiversity and the Centre of economic mountain research CE-MONT from the Romanian Academy, have the availability to join an important consortiums in order to access special funds destined to rural development in the mountain zone.

4. Conclusions

At European level it is necessary a ***Common Mountain Policy (PMC)*** based on a distinct financial exercise and developed through Regional Mountain Stations, representative for the main mountain ranges from Europe. Thus, a serious reflection for the mountain zone will have the necessary frame to elaborate mountain programs and subprograms. It may be imposed an European vision of the mountain, necessary for implementing equality of chances in the mountain zone, in order to economically increase this zone in comparison to the others, i.e. to install a solidarity, an adaptation and a special governing for the mountain zone to withstand the future conditions.

It becomes extremely opportune and urgent a ***Strategy of sustainable development of the Mountain Zone from Romania, integrated with the European strategy of the Mountain***, strategy of multiannual type. It must be mentioned that this strategy must not be modified in function of the changes of political cycles, because the mountain responds slower and needs time.

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